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METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D3.2

Human rights impact assessment (first version)

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Terms and abbreviations

ABC	Automated Border Control
BMS	Border Management System
CFR	EU Charter of Fundamental Rights
DOA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EC	European Commission
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Board
EES	Entry/exit system
ENISA	European Union Agency for Network and Information Security
ETIAS	European Travel Information and Authorisation System
FER	Facial Emotion Recognition
FRA	Fundamental Rights Agency
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HRIA	Human Rights Impact Assessment
RFID	Radio frequency identification
RTP	Registered traveller program
SBC	Schengen Borders Code
SIS	Schengen Information System
TCN	Third country nationals
EEA	European economic area
EU	European Union
VIS	Visa Information System

Executive Summary

This document is Deliverable D3.2 “Human rights impact assessment (first version)” of the METICOS project.

In the context of WP3, this Deliverable seeks to identify, evaluate and address the adverse effects on human rights emerging from the METICOS project, and in turn, prevent the METICOS components from breaching fundamental rights and/or negatively impacting socio-cultural factors.

In order to achieve its aim, this Deliverable:

- identifies the scope of the Human Rights Impact Assessment (HRIA);
- identifies the impacted groups of persons and lists the possibly impacted human rights;
- evaluates the impacts of the METICOS platform on human rights;
- formulates mitigation measures;
- provides for an audit and review stage of the HRIA.

The assessment process began at the inception of the project (M03) and will carry on throughout its lifetime (M36). During its process, it will analyse all stages of the development process of METICOS to gain an understanding of how each component has approached human rights intersectionality from every aspect of its development.

It is important to note that, in line with the DoA, this Deliverable (D3.2) consists of a “first version of the report on human rights impact assessment”. By consequence, this Deliverable should be considered as an interim version. A second final version of the Human rights impact assessment will be submitted on M30.

1 Introduction

1.1 General description of METICOS

The efficient processing of an ever-increasing number of travellers at EU borders calls for more flexible, automated and scalable “no-gate” border security solutions. A “No-Gate Border Crossing Point Solution” is understood to be “a method which enables travellers to cross borders without being slowed down by physical checks, based on automated risk-assessment and/or biometric verification processes”¹. Recent regulatory efforts made by the EU in the context of the “Smart Borders initiative” are meant to frame no-gate border solutions. With this regard, during METICOS’ life cycle (2020-2023), a number of key transformations are planned to take place. Among these, two new systems are expected to have a big impact on the border crossing experience: the Entry/Exit System (EES)², with planned entry into operation in the first quarter of 2022, and the European Travel Information and Authorization System (ETIAS)³, planned to be operational by the end 2022.

Concretely, “no gate solutions” – which play an important role in the automation of the clearance process of travellers during security border control – include, amongst others, “airport mobile apps, self-service kiosk check-ins, smart boarding gates, and self-service baggage drop, tagging and tracking, along with biometric technologies”⁴. According to the European Commission, “one main challenge is to manage the flow of travellers and goods arriving at our external borders, while at the same time tackling irregular migration and enhancing our internal security. Any novel technology or organisational measure will need to be accepted by the European citizens”⁵.

In this context, METICOS aims to introduce tools and methods being used in the field of Big Data Analysis in the context of border management in order to evaluate the user’s acceptance and the efficiency of modern control technologies of EU borders such as “no gate solutions”. It is therefore positioned as “an initiative to create a real-time decision-support system with regard to different Smart

¹ S. BINDER et al. “Biometric technology in “no-gate border crossing solutions” under consideration of privacy, ethical, regulatory and social acceptance.” In *Multimedia tools and applications*, 2020, pp. 1-14.

² The Entry/Exit System (EES) will be an automated IT system for registering travellers from third-countries, both short-stay visa holders and visa exempt travellers, each time they cross an EU external border. The system will register the person’s name, type of the travel document, biometric data (fingerprints and captured facial images) and the date and place of entry and exit. It will also record refusals of entry. EES will replace the current system of manual stamping of passports, which is time consuming, does not provide reliable data on border crossings and does not allow a systematic detection of over-stayers (travellers who have exceeded the maximum duration of their authorised stay).

³ ETIAS will be a largely automated IT system created to identify security, irregular migration or high epidemic risks posed by visa-exempt visitors travelling to the Schengen States, whilst at the same time facilitate crossing borders for the vast majority of travellers who do not pose such risks. Non-EU nationals who do not need a visa to travel to the Schengen area will have to apply for a travel authorisation through the ETIAS system prior to their trip. The ETIAS travel authorisation will be a mandatory pre-condition for entry to the Schengen States. It will be checked together with the travel documents by the border guards when crossing the EU border. This prior verification of visa exempt non-EU citizens will facilitate border checks; avoid bureaucracy and delays for travellers when presenting themselves at the borders; ensure a coordinated and harmonised risk assessment of third-country nationals; and substantially reduce the number of refusals of entry at border crossing points.

⁴ PERSONA, “D2.1: A study of latest and new generation no-gate crossing point solutions”, p. 17, available at

⁵ H2020 call “SU-BES01-2018-2019-2020”.

Border control technologies that empower three major stakeholder groups within the European border control sector (i.e., travellers and border control authorities & service providers) to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency. To this end, the METICOS project will develop a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and users' acceptance of border control technologies. The proposed platform will provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision-makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions"⁶.

METICOS will be demonstrated in pilot implementations involving informed and consenting participants playing the role of travellers and border control staff. Only adults (persons over 18 years of age) having the capacity to consent will be recruited for the purpose of the METICOS pilots. More detailed information about the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants can be found in D1.1 – "H – Requirement No. 2".

1.2 Document objective and scope

The METICOS consortium places high value on identifying, evaluating and assessing whether the foreseen research activities and expected results will respect and promote fundamental rights in accordance and compliance with the European Convention on Human Rights⁷ and the EU's Charter of Fundamental Rights⁸.

The METICOS platform 1) aims to measure user's acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies 2) by using methods and tools used in the field of Big Data Analysis. Hence two main areas of concern need to be assessed from a Human Rights perspective:

1. The general aim of the METICOS platform is to explore travellers' attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance. According to the Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA), "Travellers' attitudes towards technologies are an important element when assessing how new measures will be received. They can help authorities forecast possible reactions and address existing fears or concerns. At the same time, travellers' perceptions are only one element to take into account when assessing fundamental rights compliance of certain measures. Violations of fundamental rights may occur regardless of whether the individual consents or not to a certain treatment, particularly in light of limited rights awareness"⁹. In short, even when modern border control technologies are being accepted by its users, technologies monitored by METICOS may entail risks for fundamental rights that need to be explored. Therefore, the views of the different target groups on a number of fundamental rights aspects related to the use of border control technologies should be sought.

⁶ METICOS's Description of Action, p. 2.

⁷ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, 1950, as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14, supplemented by Protocols Nos. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13 and 16.

⁸ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 26 October 2012, 2012/C 326/02.

⁹ FRA, Survey in the framework of the eu-LISA pilot on smart borders – travellers' views on and experiences of smart borders, Smart borders pilot final report - annexes, November 2015, p.307, available at https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/what-we-do/policies/borders-and-visas/smart-borders/docs/smart_borders_pilot_-_technical_report_annexes_en.pdf

2. The methods and technologies being used in METICOS in order to pursue its aim stem from the field of “Big Data Analysis”. The term “Big Data” usually identifies extremely large data sets that may be analysed computationally to extract inferences about data patterns, trends, and correlations¹⁰. According to the International Telecommunication Union, Big Data are “a paradigm for enabling the collection, storage, management, analysis and visualization, potentially under real-time constraints, of extensive datasets with heterogeneous characteristics”¹¹. The Council of Europe highlights that “the valuable insights provided by Big Data change the manner in which society can be understood and organised. Not all data processed in a big data context concern personal data and human interaction but a large spectrum of it does, with a direct impact on individuals and their rights with regard to the processing of personal data. Furthermore, since Big Data makes it possible to collect and analyse large amounts of data to identify attitude patterns and predict behaviours of groups and communities, the collective dimension of the risks related to the use of data is also to be considered”¹². Hence, in METICOS, measures must be taken in order to prevent the potential negative impact of the use of Big Data on human dignity, human rights, and fundamental individual and collective freedoms¹³.

By consequence, potential impacts on human rights may derive from the overall objective of the METICOS project but also from the big data tools and methods being used. Table 1 below illustrates both the METICOS objective and the tools being used, the origin of human rights concerns and the potential impacts on human rights.

Table 1- Human right implications deriving from METICOS objectives and tools/methods

	METICOS objective	METICOS Big Data tools and methods
Description	The METICOS platform measures the social acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies by EU citizens and third-country nationals.	The METICOS platform is a set of components which aim to measure user’s acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies by using methods and tools used in the field of Big Data Analysis.
Origin of human	Border control checks carried out by border management authorities to verify if a person is entitled to enter the	The METICOS platform converts secondary statistical data coming from the different BCP databases as well as primary data

¹⁰ Council of Europe, Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of Big Data, Strasbourg, 23 January 2017, P. 4, available at <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=09000016806ebe7a>

¹¹ Ibidem.

¹² Ibidem.

¹³ It should be noted, however, that the impacts of the METICOS platforms on the rights to privacy and data protection are analysed in a separate set of deliverables, namely D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”, due on M12 and D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26

<p>right concerns</p>	<p>territory of an EU Member State have implications on fundamental rights.</p> <p>Moreover, the Smart Border Control technologies of which the acceptance by EU citizens and third-country nationals is envisioned to be monitored by the METICOS system include large-scale personal information systems combined with personal identity verification systems, which largely involve automated multi-biometrics-based authentication methods.</p>	<p>provided by border staff and travellers (questionnaires, METICOS mobile & tablet applications, Twitter), into anonymized metrics and KPIs that enable evidence-based decisions for authorities and decision makers based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.</p>
<p>Potential impacts on Human Rights</p>	<p>The Smart Border Control technologies of which the acceptance and efficiency are envisioned to be monitored by the METICOS platform are not as human rights and gender-neutral as they seem to be. These technologies may have unintended and unforeseen, but important, effects on the fundamental rights of travellers.</p> <p>Hence, it is important to ensure that the METICOS system takes into account the potential impacts on human rights deriving from the border control technologies of which the acceptance and efficiency are being measured.</p>	<p>The data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform in order to measure the users' acceptance and the efficiency of border control technologies might impact the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.</p> <p>Given the work that has been carried out in the DPIA, the aim of this HRIA is not to duplicate the work conducted in D3.1 by analysing the impacts of the METICOS platform on the rights to privacy and data protection. However, as these two rights are essential to the free development of an individual's personality and identity, these rights also facilitate the enjoyment of other human rights. By consequence, any breach of privacy or data protection requirements identified in D3.1 might also have consequences on other human rights such as freedom of speech, freedom of thought, freedom of movement, prohibition of discrimination, right to liberty, conscience and religion, etc</p>

For both the technologies being monitored by METICOS and the big data tools/methods being used in the platform, this task (T3.3) seeks to ensure that human rights are being respected.

The assessment process began at the inception of the project (M03) and will carry on throughout its lifetime (M36). It analyses all stages of the development process to gain an understanding of how each component has approached human rights intersectionality from every aspect of its development. The

result will answer one question: does the proposed tool breach human rights, directly or indirectly, in any way possible?

It is important to note that, in line with the DoA, this Deliverable (D3.2) consists of a “first version of the report on human rights impact assessment”. Hence, this document should be considered as an interim version. A second final version of the Human rights impact assessment will be submitted on M30.

1.3 Methodological approach

1.3.1 Aim of the human rights impact assessment

According to the DoA, this Deliverable (D3.2) should consist of a Human Right Impact Assessment of the METICOS platform.

Generally speaking, an impact assessment *“is an evaluation technique used to analyse the possible consequences of an initiative for a relevant societal concern or concerns (that is, a matter or matters of interest or importance), if this initiative could present danger to these concerns, with a view to supporting an informed decision on whether to deploy the initiative and under what conditions, and it constitutes – in the first place – a means to protect those societal concerns”*¹⁴.

A human rights impact assessment (hereafter “HRIA”) can be defined as *“a continuous process for identifying, comprehending, evaluating and addressing the adverse effects emerging from a business project or from activities on the enjoyment of human rights enjoyment by impacted rights-holders”*¹⁵.

1.3.2 Methodology

Conducting an HRIA involves several phases or steps, all of which need to be included to ensure a comprehensive assessment:

1. Identification of the scope of the HRIA
2. Identification of the impacted groups and the impacted human rights
3. Evaluation of the impacts on human rights
4. Formulation and implementation of mitigation measures
5. Audit and review of the HRIA

This methodology is inspired from the one being proposed in the SATORI project¹⁶ which reflects both the existing literature and the R&I practice.

¹⁴ Kloza, D, Van Dijk, N, Casiraghi, S, Vazquez Maymir, S, Roda, S, Tanas, A & Konstantinou, I 2019, 'Towards a method for data protection impact assessment: Making sense of GDPR requirements' *d.pia.lab Policy Brief*, vol. 1, no. 2019, p.1, available at https://cris.vub.be/ws/portalfiles/portal/48091346/dpialab_pb2019_1_final.pdf

¹⁵ Nora Götzmann, Tulika Bansal, Elin Wrzoncki, Cathrine Poulsen-Hansen, Jacqueline Tedaldi and Roya Høvsgaard, *Human rights impact assessment guidance and toolbox*, The Danish Institute for Human Rights, 2016, p.9, available at https://www.socialimpactassessment.com/documents/hria_guidance_and_toolbox_final_jan2016.pdf

¹⁶ SATORI, Annex 1 of Deliverable D4.1, “A Common Framework for Ethical Impact Assessment”, October 2016.

The figure hereunder depicts the different steps of HRIA conducted in METICOS. The audit and review of the HRIA stage run separate from the other four stages, as it applies to the entirety of the process.

Figure 1- Methodology of METICOS' HRIA

The table below provides a summarized overview of the concrete steps of each of the stages of the HRIA conducted in this Deliverable.

Table 2 - Concrete steps of each of the stages of the HRIA

Step	Description
Identify the scope of the HRIA	This step, based on the initial description, is taken to determine the extent of the assessment process of the METICOS project outputs.

	<p>Potential impacts on human rights may derive from the overall objective of the METICOS project (measurement of the acceptance and efficiency of border technologies) but also from the big data tools and methods being used. By consequence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scope of this HRIA should take into account potential impacts on human rights deriving from the border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform. • The scope of this HRIA should cover the “METICOS platform”, which is understood as being the platform being described in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.
<p>Identify the impacted groups of persons and the potentially impacted Human rights</p>	<p>This step consists of the identification of the groups of persons being impacted by the border technologies being monitored as well as by the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform.</p> <p>The goal is to list the possible human rights concerns that may be touched on.</p>
<p>Evaluate the impacts on Human Rights</p>	<p>This step is aimed at evaluating the relative importance of human rights impacts that have been determined in the previous step.</p>
<p>Formulate and implement mitigation measures</p>	<p>In this step, concrete, detailed measures (controls, safeguards, solutions, etc.) for addressing the impacts on Human Rights are proposed to minimize the negative impacts of the planned initiative and, if possible, to maximize the positive ones. Concretely, this step will result in findings and recommendations to the METICOS consortium.</p>
<p>Review and audit of the HRIA</p>	<p>The review and audit stage of the HRIA aims at ensuring independent evaluation of the HRIA process and, if necessary, of independent intervention. It especially focuses on the finalization of the HRIA, by reviewing and assessing whether the process has been successfully conducted and whether the consortium has ensured follow-ups of the relevant findings. However, the review and audit stage also plays a role during the entire HRIA process, for it can steer the process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.</p> <p>Concretely, the review step will be carried out by hosting a virtual workshop with partners and external stakeholders to evaluate findings and to together weigh the impact by asking how the METICOS project will contribute to equality, dignity and</p>

	<p>autonomy, as well as to assess the foreseen impact on gender relations.</p> <p>It should also be noted that, in accordance with D1.8 “GEN - Requirement No. 11”, the Ethical Board is competent to “independently and critically appraise the activities of the project undertaken in its lifetime, as well as the foreseen use of the system in an operational context after the life of the project”. By consequence, the HRIA will be submitted to the Ethical Board in order to be audited.</p>
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1.4 Relations with other deliverables

Although this Deliverable (D3.2) is a standalone document, it is strongly interconnected with several other METICOS deliverables:

- Deliverable D1.1 is addressing the question of the participation of human beings during the research and pilots of the METICOS project. It also contains templates of the forms of consent and the information sheet.
- Deliverable D1.2 presents a list of the representatives of the Ethical Committees of the METICOS partners. The deliverable identifies the Ethical Committees of each partner of the METICOS Consortium to ensure their approval in case such approval is needed (i.e., engaging human subjects). The Ethical Committees must authorize the METICOS pilot projects before their implementation.
- Deliverable D1.6 deals with the safety measures followed for the staff involved in the METICOS project.
- Deliverable 1.7 deals with the potential misuse of data before, during, and after the implementation of the METICOS project.
- Deliverable D1.8 establishes an independent Ethical Board to monitor the ethics issues in the METICOS project and how they are handled. The members of the Ethical Board may raise any ethical or legal issue related to the METICOS project and must be consulted at least on the ethics issues raised in the ethics screening report. It is important to highlight that the HRIA conducted in this Deliverable will be submitted to the Ethical Board in order to obtain its opinion and recommendations for future work to be included in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”, due on M30.
- In the context of METICOS, a specific Deliverable (D3.1) is dedicated to examine the privacy and data protection impacts of the METICOS’s platform by conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). A DPIA is “a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data⁴ by assessing them and determining

the measures to address them”. By consequence, this Deliverable (D3.2) is not meant to duplicate the work conducted in D3.1 by analysing the impacts of the METICOS platform on the rights to privacy and data protection but instead will focus on identifying and mitigating the impacts of METICOS on other human rights listed in International and European instruments.

1.5 Document structure

The structure of this document is as follows:

- Section 1 provides for an introductory description of the document explaining its objectives, methodology, relation with other Deliverables and its structure.
- Section 2 defines the scope of the Human Right Impact Assessment (HRIA), which is twofold. The scope of the HRIA covers both 1) the border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform and 2) the METICOS platform itself.
- Section 3 consists into the identification of the groups of persons being impacted both by the border control technologies being monitored by the METICOS platform and by the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform. This section also aims at identifying and listing the target groups’ human rights which are potentially being impacted.
- Section 4 aims at evaluating the relative importance of human rights impacts that have been determined in the previous step.
- Section 5 summarizes the mitigation measures and the recommendations having been identified.
- Section 6 provides for 1) a review stage aiming to evaluate the findings of this HRIA so as to provide constructive feedback for improving the execution of the HRIA process and 2) an audit stage conducted by the Ethical Board with the aim to steer the HRIA process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.

2 Scope of the HRIA

The scope of the HRIA conducted in this Deliverable covers both 1) the border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform and 2) the METICOS platform itself, which is understood as being the combination of technologies/components presented in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

2.1 Scope 1: Identification of border control technologies being monitored by METICOS

The first scope of the HRIA covers the border control technologies intended to be monitored by the METICOS platform. In particular, the METICOS platform envisages to evaluate the efficiency and acceptance of “no-gate border crossing point solutions”. For the purposes of this Deliverable, a “No-Gate Border Crossing Point Solution” is understood to be “a method which enables travellers to cross borders without being slowed down by physical checks, based on automated risk-assessment and/or biometric verification processes”¹⁷.

The installation and use of special equipment such as self-service kiosks, ABC gates (Automated Border Control), also referred to as e-gates (electronic gates) and biometric equipment for border guards pose human rights concerns that should not be underestimated.

The table below lists examples of no-gate solutions being currently used in EU member states¹⁸.

Table 3 - No-gate solutions currently used in EU member states

Border control technology solution	Description
BorderXpress	From the information provided on BorderXpress website, by using this technology, travellers may be in the position to independently scan their identity card or passport as an intermediate step of the passport control procedure. A traveller needs to approach a kiosk and place its open passport into the scanner. The kiosk uses facial recognition technology to compare the traveller’s face to the photograph recorded on the chip in the traveller’s passport (fingerprints matching is also possible in the new version of BorderXpress) and then proceeds to border authority checks. The traveller then receives a receipt which should be presented “face to face” to a border guard at a predefined checkpoint.

¹⁷ S. BINDER et al. “Biometric technology in “no-gate border crossing solutions” under consideration of privacy, ethical, regulatory and social acceptance.” In Multimedia tools and applications, 2020, pp. 1-14.

¹⁸ The information provided in this table has been extracted from public sources, mainly the websites of airports and other cross border points as well as the websites of the providers of the technologies listed below and other publication made online. The information provided has not been cross checked with either the service providers or with the user of these technologies.

	<p>Kiosks enable the use of a two-step process that frees border control authorities from cumbersome administrative functions, such as data entry, biometric collection, etc. The first step moves administrative functions to the self-serve kiosks and a second step of document verification and supervision by border officers. The second step adds a level of security by empowering the border officer to have the final approval to allow a traveller into the country.</p>
<p>BKC-Kordon</p>	<p>According to Bancomzvjazok’s website, “The bkc-KORDON system is intended to control the flow of passengers and vehicles crossing the state border and can be applied to automobile, air, sea and pedestrian crossing points. Flexible system scalability and configuration of its parameters for individual requirements. Interoperability with external systems and sources of information (Interpol, SIS)” .</p> <p>The system "GART-1/P" works at all checkpoints: airports, railway, automobile, etc., and there are more than 2000 workplaces. Every workplace is equipped with software and hardware. On stationary workplaces "CONDOR", is used, and in mobile workplaces, the mobile terminal BPT800 is used.</p> <p>CONDOR is a full-page document reader with built-in computer for passport control:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Automatic reading and checking of documents in 3 seconds ○ Validation of passports, ID-cards, driver’s licenses, visas and other documents, including RFID-based contactless identification circuits (RFID) ○ Check listings (Stop List) and databases using on-line services ○ Recognition of text information <p>BPT800 is a portable solution for the registration and control of persons crossing security checkpoints. It provides high-quality and fast fixation of biometric data. The time for reading and processing information is up to 5 seconds. Through the use of the terminal BPT800, the passport and biometric control at any checkpoint takes no more than 20 seconds. The BPT800 Portable Terminal is made in a shock-, dust-, and waterproof enclosure. The protection degree of the case is IP67, and the protection degree of the finger scanner is IP65. The BPT800 functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ automatic readout from the machine-readable zone (MRZ) and electronic document chips (RFID) ○ recognition of text and biometric data (ICAO Document 9303) ○ fingerprint scanning (FBI) ○ verification of compliance and reliability of documents on databases ○ support for the ability to enter data manually ○ definition and fixing of GPS coordinates ○ continuous operation time – 8 hours ○ data transfer using GSM, GPRS, Wi-Fi

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ a system developers’ kit (SDK) for adapting the terminal to use in existing information systems.
<p>Thales Gemalto EU EES Border Management System</p>	<p>Thales BMS Solution enables a 2-step border clearance, using biometric-enabled self-service kiosks for performing traveller pre-checks and data collection and have the Border Officer handling the border clearance. The 2-Step process consists of a registration step, performed in self-service mode by the traveller using kiosk and a border clearance final step, performed either through a manual border clearance handled by the border officer or through automated e-gates.</p> <p>Once a registered traveller goes to a stationary manual border control booth, where the information pre-enrolled at the Kiosk can be retrieved immediately thanks to a Single Identity Token (or passport or fingerprint). The Border Clearance application automatically identifies the traveller (live face capture through integrated camera) and triggers the traveller’s profile. With the dedicated a web-based application the border guard can complete traveller border clearance and enrol the passenger into the EES.</p> <p>As an alternative to manual control booths, Thales Gemalto also develops ABC gates. With ABC, a traveller can pass the second step in a matter of seconds. Automation of Border control can leverage an array of different equipment, from a 2 door ABC gate or smaller one door gates.</p>
<p>PARAFE</p>	<p>PARAFE (Passage Automatisé Rapide Des Frontières Extérieures) is a self-service automated system that uses biometric technology to help travellers to cross border faster and independently in the Groupe ADP which owns and manages Parisian international airports. This service is valid for European citizens holding a biometric passport. Paris Aéroport, together with the Ministry of Home Affairs have deployed within Paris-Charles de Gaulle and Paris-Orly airports a new generation of gates which includes facial authentication technology.</p> <p>The 2 different options for this service:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facial authentication (passport, boarding pass and face) - Fingerprint authentication (passport, boarding pass and fingerprint) <p>The passenger presents himself at the entrance of an automated tunnel. He places his biometric passport, open to the photo page, on the document reader, following the instructions on the screen.</p> <p>After reading the data, the tunnel door opens. The passenger enters the tunnel, positions himself at the floor marking and follows the instructions on the screen in front of him. The passenger must be careful not to interfere with the closing of the entrance doors with his luggage. Once the authentication is completed, the exit doors open and the passenger can cross the border. On average, it takes about 20 seconds to cross the border.</p>

<p>EasyPASS</p>	<p>EasyPASS is an ABC System (e-Gates) that verifies the identity of the traveller and the validity and authenticity of their electronic travel document. Individuals must place their passport on the document reader with the data page face down. After the passport has been recognized, the door to the lane will open. In the lane, individuals must look directly at the camera located above the monitor in the exit door. The system then compares the passport photo to the live image.</p> <p>Holders of electronic passports (ePassports) from the European Union, the European Economic Area and Switzerland can use EasyPASS to enter and leave the Schengen area. Individuals must be at least 12 years old. German nationals also have the possibility of using the automated border control system with the new German identity card.</p> <p>Moreover, holders of electronic passports (ePassports) from countries that signed a mutual agreement to use automated border control procedures are now eligible to use EasyPASS-RTP to enter and leave the Schengen area – provided that they are at least 18 years old and registered with the Federal Police.</p> <p>Such agreements currently exist with the United States of America and Hong Kong Special Administrative Region Peoples Republic of China. Other third countries may follow.</p> <p>To participate in EasyPASS-RTP, individuals must visit an enrolment centre at a German airport using EasyPASS. There, they will be informed about the enrolment procedure and the data protection policy. They will then be asked to sign a form to confirm your voluntary participation in EasyPASS-RTP and consent to the storage of your personal data. Afterwards the Federal Police will check whether they meet the participation requirements by means of a questionnaire.</p> <p>Following this procedure, the Federal Police checks the validity and authenticity of the travel document and whether there are any security issues that prohibit participation in a RTP. In order to achieve this, the Federal Police checks the data against the available police information systems.</p> <p>Provided that there are no objections for security reasons, the personal data of the voluntary individuals will be stored in the EasyPASS-RTP database of the Federal Police.</p> <p>When using the ABC gate, after successful face recognition, registered travellers (RTs) from outside the EU - in contrast to the usual EasyPASS procedure - will see a special symbol and have to wait until a border guard opens the exit door. RTs then have to move forward to the monitoring booth, which is located directly behind the EasyPASS gate. An officer will then check the additional entry requirements and stamp the passport. After that procedure the border check is completed.</p>
<p>RAPID</p>	<p>The RAPID system is based on facial recognition and allows automated border crossing of passengers holding EU/EEA electronic passports.</p>

It should also be noted that the METICOS platform will be demonstrated in pilot implementations. The table below lists the technologies which, at the time of writing this Deliverable, are envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform during the pilots. During the project lifetime, changes might occur in the number of pilots being envisaged, the countries where these pilots are likely to happen, the description of the pilots, and the technologies envisaged being monitored. In case such changes arise, these will be reported in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”, which is due on M30.

Table 4 - Technologies envisaged to be monitored during the pilots

Border control technology	Country of UC	Use-Case Title	Use-Case Description
Optical reader, fingerprint reader, license plate reading machine, smell dog, video endoscope, tactical mirror	Romania	Evaluation of the document verification and fingerprint reader in TIMISOARA BCP	3 citizens of German nationality (father, mother and son) present themselves for entering Romania, declaring at the border control the fact that they want to travel to Romania to visit the BRAN castle. Before entering Romania, they should pass through the document verification and fingerprint reader control. The received information will be matched with the local authority, SIS, VIS and INTERPOL databases.
Boarding pass scanner, BorderXpress kiosk	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document / non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) - Departures - No hits found	European traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Boarding pass scanner, BorderXpress kiosk, passport reader	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document / non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone	European traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.

		(MRZ) - Departures - Hits found	
BorderXpress kiosk	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document / non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) - Arrivals - No hits found	European traveller is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.
BorderXpress kiosk, passport reader	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document / non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) - Arrivals - Hits found	European traveller is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) / Third Country Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel	European / Third Country traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.

		Document - Departures - No Hits found	
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ)/ Third Country Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel Document - Departures - Hits found	European / Third Country traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) / Third Country Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel Document - Arrivals - No Hits found	European / Third Country traveller is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) /	European / Third Country traveler is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.

		Third Country Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel Document - Arrivals - Hits found	
Passport reader, Ultraviolet light, national entry-exit system	Cyprus	Border checks at Larnaca and Paphos airports - arrival	Border checks at Cyprus airports, Larnaca and Paphos, are carried out by Immigration Officers of the Aliens and Immigration Unit of the Cyprus Police.
Automatic electronic entry gates (e-gates), BorderXpress interactive kiosks, Passport Reader, Ultraviolet light, Stamp machine, national entry-exit system	Cyprus	Border checks at Larnaca and Paphos airports - departure	Border checks at Cyprus airports, Larnaca and Paphos, are carried out by Immigration Officers of the Aliens and Immigration Unit of the Cyprus Police.
ABC System Control (for EU citizen with EU Biometric Passport), Manual Border Control (for TCN national), UV light, live scan for fingers, magnifier, e-passport reader	Greece	Flight from ATH to non-Schengen airport	An EU citizen and his wife, third-country national, travel from Athens airport to Dubai. The man holds an EU biometric passport. Therefore he passes through the ABC System and the woman holds a non-EU passport, so she is submitted to manual border control.
PIKO, document scanner REGULA, document control software DocCheck, Dermalog fingerprint scanner	Estonia	Fixing of the border crossing of a third-country national to the Border Control Information	Border checks of third-country nationals

		System (hereinafter as PIKO)	
PIKO, Document Scanner REGULA, DocCheck Software	Estonia	Capturing EU/EEA/Schengen citizen's border crossing data into the PIKO	EU/EEA/Schengen citizen's border crossing check
PIKO, national and international database	Estonia	Referral of person to second-line check (step 2)	Referral of a person to the second line check in case of hits or suspicion
DIXI -01 -01UW, Mirror kits(OAD-4), Data base GART 1-P	To be decided	The procedure of border control for vehicle border crossing point	The procedure of border control for vehicle border crossing point

2.2 Scope 2: Description of the METICOS system

The second scope of the HRIA conducted covers the METICOS platform which is being developed during the project. The “METICOS platform” is understood as being the combination of technologies/components listed in D3.1– “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

The purpose of the METICOS platform is to monitor the use of border control technologies with the aim of exploring both travellers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.

Given the data processing operations being carried out by the METICOS platform, human rights concerns, mostly related to privacy and data protection, must be taken into account.

The table below explains how the METICOS platform generally works. More details about the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform are available in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

Table 5 -Lifecycle of data within the METICOS platform

Processes	Description of the process
1. Statistical (anonymous) data are collected from border crossing points databases.	Statistical and anonymous data are collected from the databases of end-user organizations (border control crossing points). These statistical data are being processed by the “Universal connector” and by the “Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems ¹⁹ ” in order to ensure uniform access to the various data sources based on authentication/authorization schemes and on profile-privileges and user rights.
2. Personal data are collected on Twitter (and possibly other social media sources) as well as on Blogs/Websites.	Public tweets (and possibly data originating from other social media sources ²⁰) as well as online reviews on Blogs/Websites regarding acceptance of border control technologies by travelers are collected. The goal is to derive the sentiments that people have towards border control.
3. Personal data are collected directly from	Personal data are collected directly from users via the METICOS Mobile Application), the METICOS tablet Application, questionnaires and

¹⁹ The Interface with Border Management Information Systems is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing statistical data that BPCs make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservices that offer information like queue lengths, average waiting times, late flights, etc and sends the data agreed with the BPC. It is important to note that the METICOS platform will not be connected with border information system like VIS, SIS or alike.

²⁰ In case data originating from other social media sources than twitter are being collected during the project, this will be described and examined in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

<p>travellers and border control staff.</p>	<p>Twitter. It should be highlighted that all primary data are collected on the basis of the consent of informed volunteers.</p>
<p>4. The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 & 3 are sent to the METICOS middleware.</p>	<p>The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 and 3 are sent to the METICOS middleware which is a software module for integration and information management of heterogeneous data sources.</p>
<p>5. In parallel with step 4, the data collected in steps 1, 2 & 3 are stored in the Data Integration Module.</p>	<p>The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 and 3 are stored in the Data Integration Module. At this stage of the project, it is envisaged to store the data processed by the METICOS platform on METICOS’s servers.</p>
<p>6. The data originating from steps 4 & 5 are being processed by the Big Data Analytics Engine.</p>	<p>The data originating from the METICOS middleware which are stored in the Data Integration Module are sent to the Big Data Analytics Engine. The Big Data Analytics Engine is composed of several sub-components: the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module, the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module and the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module. The general aim of the Big Data Analytics Engine is to uncover hidden patterns amongst attributes of gathered data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.</p>
<p>7. The data originating from step 6 are sent to the Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module.</p>	<p>The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travellers, border authorities).</p>
<p>8. The data originating from steps 6 & 7 are sent to the Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA).</p>	<p>The aim of the Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA) is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyze correlations of data generated from other METICOS components as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies.</p>
<p>9. The data originating from steps 6 & 7 are sent to the Social Toolkit Module.</p>	<p>The social sensing tool is a technology acceptance prediction system for border control technologies. The social sensing tool will analyze and estimate the activity and interactions between migrants/travelers, border staff and border control technologies for technology acceptance prediction.</p>
<p>10. The data originating from steps 8 & 9 are sent to the Personnel Front-End.</p>	<p>After the authorized border control personnel logs in to the system, the Dashboard screen is displayed. Its purpose is to display an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the</p>

	<p>acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. Some of those metrics might include star ratings over time, speed, ease of use, emotional response. They will be displayed using graphs, pie charts and histograms that span a certain time period that may be selected by the user. The user will also have the ability to view analytics for specific checkpoints as well as aggregated analytics for all checkpoints.</p>
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In order to have an overview of the necessity of the processing carried out by each component of the METICOS system, a questionnaire has been sent to METICOS’ technology providers with the aim to understand:

1. What is being addressed by these components?
2. Why are these components being considered as a solution to these issues?

Answers to this questionnaire may be found in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

In addition, in order to ensure data security, the following controls are envisaged to be implemented²¹:

- Statistical data originating from the border crossing points databases are anonymized before being sent to the METICOS platform.
- Logical access control verifies that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to the anonymized data originating from the border crossing points.
- Logical access control verifies that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to any primary or secondary data collected by the METICOS platform.
- Primary and secondary data are being encrypted when stored on the METICOS servers (in the Data integration module).
- After having been processed by the METICOS components, all primary and secondary data are being anonymized before being sent to the Personnel Front-End. The general security goal is to avoid that non-anonymized data could be made available to authorized border control authorities or decision makers. Indeed, the overall purpose of the METICOS platform is to provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers via the End-User Front-End. Hence access to non-anonymized data to the end-users should strictly be avoided.
- Access control verifies that only authorized border control authorities and decision makers have access to the anonymized data made available via the Personnel Front-End.

²¹ At this stage of the project, the technical system architecture and specifications of the METICOS platform have not been defined yet. Hence the following data security measures must still be confirmed. This will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

The figure below describes a first draft of data flow diagram enriched with security features²².

²² This diagram could be modified during the duration of the project. A final diagram will be included in D3.6 “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

Figure 2 - Data flow diagram enriched with security features

3 Identification of impacted groups of persons and impacted Human rights

3.1 Identification of the impacted groups of persons

This step consists of the identification of the groups of persons being impacted:

- 1) by the border control technologies being monitored by the METICOS platform ;
- 2) by the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform.

3.1.1 Identification of groups of persons being impacted by border control technologies

When assessing the impacts on human rights of border control technologies which are envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform, an important step is to identify the groups of persons susceptible to be impacted by such technologies.

3.1.1.1 *Categories of travellers in the Schengen Border Code*

The primary persons or groups of persons impacted by border control technologies are of course the travellers themselves.

However, “there are many different travellers to consider, each with local, regional and national conflicting interests and values”²³. In order to categorize this multitude, from a legal point of view, a possibility is to refer to the travellers’ categories in the Schengen Borders Code²⁴ (hereafter “SBC”), which can be divided into two macro-categories: 1) Persons enjoying the Union right of free movement and 2) Third country nationals²⁵.

The main reason for this distinction is that, according to the SBC, in principle, persons enjoying the Union right of free movement, on the one hand, and third-country nationals (hereafter “TCNs”), on the other, are subject to different border control checks. Members of the first group are subject only to a “minimum check” on entry/exit of the Schengen Area, while members of the second to a more thorough one.

The table below lists which border checks, in principle, must be carried out at the external borders for each category of travellers in the SBC.

²³ PERSONA, “D5.2 – PERSONA textbook of assessment of no-gate crossing point solutions (1st version)”, p. 81.

²⁴ Consolidated text of Regulation (EU) 2016/399 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on a Union Code on the rules governing the movement of persons across borders (Schengen Borders Code) (codification), available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0399-20190611>

²⁵ This distinction is based on article 8 of the Schengen Border Code.

Table 6 - Border checks which may be carried out at the external borders

Category of travelers in the SBC	Border checks which must be carried out at external borders according to article 8 of the SBC
Persons enjoying the right of free movement under Union law	<p>Persons enjoying the right of free movement under Union law must be subject to the following minimum systematic checks on entry and exit:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verification of the identity and the nationality of the person and of the authenticity and validity of the travel document for crossing the border, including by consulting the relevant databases, in particular: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) the SIS; b) Interpol’s Stolen and Lost Travel Documents (SLTD) database; c) national databases containing information on stolen, misappropriated, lost and invalidated travel documents. <p>For passports and travel documents containing a storage medium, the authenticity of the chip data must be checked.</p> 2. Verification that a person enjoying the right of free movement under Union law is not considered to be a threat to the public policy, internal security, public health or international relations of any of the Member States, including by consulting the SIS and other relevant Union databases. This is without prejudice to the consultation of national and Interpol databases. <p>Derogations from this rule of systematic checks of relevant databases are possible at land and sea borders subject to certain conditions following a specific procedure for notification of such derogation and risk assessment²⁶.</p>
Third-country nationals	<p>On entry and exit, third-country nationals must be subject to thorough checks as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verification of the identity and the nationality of the third-country national and of the authenticity and validity of the travel document for crossing the border, including by consulting the relevant databases, in particular: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) the SIS, b) Interpol’s SLTD database,

²⁶ See article 8, 2a of the SBC.

	<p>c) national databases containing information on stolen, misappropriated, lost and invalidated travel documents.</p> <p>For passports and travel documents containing an electronic storage medium (chip), the authenticity and integrity of the chip data shall be checked.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Verification that the travel document is accompanied, where applicable, by the requisite visa or residence permit. 3. Verification that the person did not exceed the maximum duration of authorized stay in the territory of the Member States; 4. Verification regarding the point of departure and the destination of the third-country national concerned and the purpose of the intended stay, checking, if necessary, the corresponding supporting documents; 5. Verification that the third-country national concerned has sufficient means of subsistence for the duration and purpose of the intended stay, for his or her return to the country of origin or transit to a third country into which he or she is certain to be admitted, or that he or she is in a position to acquire such means lawfully; 6. Verification that the third-country national concerned, his or her means of transport and the objects he or she is transporting are not likely to jeopardize the public policy, internal security, public health or international relations of any of the Member States. Such verification shall include direct consultation of the data and alerts on persons and, where necessary, objects included in the SIS and other relevant Union databases, and the action to be performed, if any, as a result of an alert. This is without prejudice to the consultation of national and Interpol databases.
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The extent of the border checks that must be carried out on entry/exit of the Schengen Area depends on whether the person being controlled is a person enjoying the right of free movement under Union law or whether that person is a third-country national. Hence these those two general categories of travellers are potentially impacted differently from a Human rights’ perspective.

In addition, it derives from the reading of the SBC that these two general categories of travellers should be sub-categorized as illustrated in the table below, depending on the travel documents and EU-scale databases that must be checked. Moreover, it is very important to also consider refugees because they are particularly affected and are more vulnerable to the risks posed by border technologies.

Table 7 - Sub-categories of impacted travellers

Category of travellers in the SBC	Sub-categories of persons that may be impacted	Travel documents that must be checked	Databases against which the traveller must be checked
Persons enjoying the right of free movement under Union law	EU/EEA/CH citizens	Identity card or passport	SIS ²⁷
	Third-country nationals who are members of the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passport • A visa, if they are nationals of a third-country subject to the visa obligation, unless they are in possession of: a valid residence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS • EES²⁹ • VIS³⁰ (if visa holder)

²⁷ The Schengen Information System (SIS) is a EU’s large-scale database aimed at ensuring a high level of security and facilitating the free movement of people within the Schengen Area through three areas of cooperation: border control, law enforcement and vehicle registration; it contains alerts on persons who may have been involved in a serious crime or may not have the right to enter or stay in the Schengen Area; on missing persons, in particular children; on certain property, such as banknotes, aircraft, boats, cars, vans, containers, firearms and identity documents, that may have been stolen, misappropriated or lost.

²⁹ The Entry/Exit System (EES) will be an automated IT system for registering travellers from third-countries, both visa holders and visa exempt travellers, each time they cross an EU external border. The system will register the person’s name, type of the travel document, biometric data (fingerprints and captured facial images) and the date and place of entry and exit. It will also record refusals of entry. EES will replace the current system of manual stamping of passports, which is time consuming, does not provide reliable data on border crossings and does not allow a systematic detection of over-stayers (travellers who have exceeded the maximum duration of their authorized stay).

³⁰ The Visa Information System (VIS), is a EU’s large-scale database that supports Member States’ consular authorities in the management of applications for short-stay visas to visit or to transit through the Schengen Area; it enables the exchange of visa information and the matching of biometric data to verify the authenticity of a visa; the VIS supports the fight against fraud and facilitates checks within the territory of the Member States, assisting in the identification of any person who may not or may no longer fulfil the conditions for entry to, stay in, or residence on the territory of the Member States; as ancillary objectives, the VIS supports the asylum applications process and contributes to the prevention of threats to internal security.

	family of a EU/EEA/CH citizen ²⁸	permit or a valid residence card	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETIAS³¹ (if no resident card or residence permit)
Third-country nationals	Third country nationals visa exempted (hereafter “TCNVE”)	Passport and valid residence permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS • EES • ETIAS
	Third country nationals visa holders (TCNVH) ³²	Passport and visa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS • EES • VIS
	Refugees	In several EU states, specific “refugee travel documents” may be issued. In the absence of valid documents, in a principle, a person who has crossed a border unlawfully, and who has no right to stay on the territory of the Member	EURODAC ³³

²⁸ To be noted that, third-country nationals who are family members of EU, EEA and CH citizens are entitled to accompany or join the EU, EEA or CH citizen for consecutive periods of up to three months per Schengen States without any conditions or formalities (except the need to have a visa for third-country nationals from a country subject to a visa requirement). When the family member travels on his/her own, the normal regime concerning the length of the short stay will (re)start to apply, as the conditions for benefiting from the facilitations concerning the free movement of the EU, EEA and CH citizens and their families are not met anymore. The previous stays performed in the area without internal border controls accompanying or joining the EU, EEA or CH citizen should not be taken into account for the sake of the calculation of the compliance with the 90/180-day rule which is applicable to the short stay only.

³¹ The European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS) will be a largely automated IT system created to identify security, irregular migration or high epidemic risks posed by visa-exempt visitors travelling to the Schengen States, whilst at the same time facilitate crossing borders for the vast majority of travellers who do not pose such risks. Non-EU nationals who do not need a visa to travel to the Schengen area will have to apply for a travel authorisation through the ETIAS system prior to their trip.

³² The lists of the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement are contained in Regulation (EU) 2018/1806 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 listing the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement.

³³ The European Dactyloscopy (Eurodac) is a the EU large-scale database for the storage of fingerprints of asylum seekers and irregular migrants aged 14 and over, which enables Member States to compare the fingerprints of asylum applicants in order to see whether they have previously applied for asylum or entered the EU irregularly via another Member State, to determine the responsibility for examining an asylum application; since July 2015, Eurodac has also been used for law enforcement purposes by Member State law enforcement authorities and Europol.

		State concerned, must be apprehended and made subject to return procedures.	
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Given that the different sub-categories of travellers listed in table 7 might have very different experiences with regard to border control technologies, it is recommended that the METICOS consortium involves each of these sub-categories during the pilots.

If it is not possible to engage with all of these sub-categories of travellers during the pilots, a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns (for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M22 and M29 – see section 6).

In addition, when presenting the pilots’ results in relation to the travellers’ acceptance level of border control technologies, these sub-categories should be differentiated (in percentages of the total of the participants).

3.1.1.2 Categories of travellers based on gender, socio-cultural factors and others

From a Human rights’s perspective, travellers may not be only impacted differently by border control technologies based on their belonging to a category or sub-category of travellers in the Schengen Border Code but also, potentially, on the factors listed in the table below:

Table 8 - Factors potentially impacting human rights of travellers

Factors potentially impacting human rights of travellers	Explanation
Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depending on the age group, (in particular children and elderly), experience with IT systems might be different Based on age, there is a risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language may be a barrier to communicate with border control authorities Based on language, there is risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accuracy and reliability of biometrics Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Nationality	Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities

Race ³⁴ /ethnicity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy and reliability of biometrics • Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Disabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disabled people could potentially face barriers when confronted to modern border control technologies and biometrics. • This factor may also lead to a risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Religious philosophical beliefs	Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Sexual orientation	Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Frequent business travellers	This category has a specific experience with border control systems.
Frequently travelling tourists	This category has a specific experience with border control systems.
Tourists that rarely travel	This category has a specific experience with border control systems.
Other	Other factors may be discussed during workshops (see section 6) and added in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”, due on M30.

Given that the different factors listed in table 8 might potentially impact the traveller’s human rights when using border control technologies, during the pilots, it is recommended that the METICOS consortium involves participants from these diverse target groups.

If it is not possible to engage with all of these target groups during the pilots, a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns (for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 – see section 6). This is particularly relevant for children since it was decided not to involve them during the pilots, as their consent to participate would not be considered as freely given (only adults over 18 with a capacity to consent will be able to participate).

In addition, when presenting the pilots’ results in relation to the travellers’ acceptance level of border control technologies, these target groups should be differentiated (in percentages of the total of the participants).

³⁴ The use of the term “race” in this Deliverable does not imply an acceptance by its users of theories which attempt to determine the existence of separate human races.

3.1.1.3 Border control staff

Aside from travellers, there are also other stakeholders to consider, especially border guards and customs who need to operate the border control technologies.

However, the impacts of border control technologies on border control staff' and customs' legitimate interests (e.g. whether they fear automated technologies would take their job away or whether they think it would reduce the overall workload) should not substituted or be confused with human rights' assessment considerations. Indeed, the scope of this HRIA is to assess the impacts on human rights, not on other legitimate interests.

Having clarified this important distinction, it is however important to get the views of border control staff on the impacts that the technologies they are operating might have on travellers' human rights.

By consequence, it is recommended to the METICOS consortium to give voice to the border control' staff opinions and views on the impacts that border control technologies might have on travellers' human rights (for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 – see section 6).

3.1.2 Identification of groups of persons being impacted by the METICOS platform

In order to identify the groups of persons being impacted by each component of the METICOS platform, a questionnaire has been sent to METICOS' technology providers. Answers are reported in the table hereunder.

Table 9 - Target groups impacted by each component of the METICOS platform

Component/ Technology	Description	Border control staff	Travellers	Other
Data Integration Module	METICOS Common Data Management Engine (CDME) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way. All the exchanged information will be translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all METICOS components use them.	N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.	N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.	
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Unstructured Data	The aim of the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module is to gather and analyse unstructured data from different sources (historical unstructured data, real-time unstructured, data gathered at pilot sites, free text in questionnaires, tweets and social media). Hence, the engine will be capable of extracting data from social media (twitter, reviews, blogs...) in a real-time automated way and storing it with the aim of further processing the data. The engine will include the functionality of sentiment detection and context detection (most important words, clustering) of social media data (twitter, reviews, blogs, etc.) in order to capture the general acceptance and social acceptance of SBC technologies. The user will be able to see most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that people are tweeting about regarding smart border control technologies.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Structured Data	The Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data will and analyse structured data coming from several sources (historical data, real-time data gathered at pilot sites, questionnaires ...). The ADME component at the end of the project will uncover hidden	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are	

	patterns amongst attributes of gathered structured data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.	consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	
Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module.	The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travelers, border authorities).	No	Yes	
Cross-sectorial (big) data analysis mechanisms	The purpose of the Cross-Sectorial Big Data Analysis (CS-BDA) Mechanisms module is to infer the acceptance of a BCP or technology by aggregating and analysing data from different sources, locations and formats. It accepts the outputs of other components (ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data, and others). The output of the CS-BDA component will be fed in the DTVA component.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	
Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit	The aim of Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA) is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyse correlations of data generated from other METICOS components as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies. It will provide a platform where the outputs from the ADME for Structured Data, ADME for Unstructured Data and CS-BDA modules will be visualised and presented.	The border control authorities will be impacted from the output of this component in the following way: This target group will be able to see and interact with a dashboard where the output of multiple METICOS components will be demonstrated and thus draw conclusions for	The anonymized data is related to the use of border control technologies by travellers	

		the general acceptance of SBC technologies per BCP but also generally (aggregated view)		
METICOS Middleware	All information coming from the data sources will be sent to the middleware module for processing and/or storage. That information will be used to perform data mining and analytics about the passengers’ perception of the technologies used at border checkpoints.	N/A: Module is not targeting a user group or role. 2) The whole system is affected by the Meticos Middleware	N/A: Module is not targeting a user group or role. 2) The whole system is affected by the Meticos Middleware	
Personel Front-End	After the authorized border control personnel logs in to the system, the Dashboard screen is displayed. Its purpose it to display an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. Some of those metrics might include star ratings over time, speed, ease of use, emotional response. They will be displayed using graphs, pie charts and histograms that span a certain time period that may be selected by the user. The user will also have the ability to view analytics for specific checkpoints as well as aggregated analytics for all checkpoints.	Yes: Users (personnel) interact with the system through Front-End	The anonymized data is related to the use of border control technologies by travellers	Anonymized data will be beneficial to societal research and decision making
Border Checkpoint and Mobile App for passengers	The passengers will be able to see the airport’s latest news, information about their flights and airport facilities, give reactions (e.g. smileys, star ratings), answer questionnaires and provide feedback through the METICOS tablet application. These functionalities can also be accessed from the passengers’ personal devices by downloading a mobile application to their cellphone. This application also enables use of the platform by people with disabilities through the use of audio based on WCAG 2.0 (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines).	Yes: Quality of the input data is important for border control authorities to obtain relevant anonymized data through the Personel Front-End.	Yes: Passengers interact with the system through this component Elder people may be not willing to participate, especially if they travel alone	

<p>Universal Connector</p>	<p>The component offers a uniform access to various data sources. It offers a standard API to access data from different data sources and hides their technological implementation details. The component has multiple connector modules that support various connection types.</p>	<p>N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.</p>	<p>N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.</p>	
<p>Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems</p>	<p>The Interface with Border Management Information Systems is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing statistical data that BPCs make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservices that offer information like queue lengths, average waiting times, late flights, etc and sends the data agreed with the BPC. It is important to note that the METICOS platform will not be connected with border information system like VIS, SIS or alike.</p>	<p>Yes: The target group for this component are Border and Customs authorities</p>	<p>No: Since this is an integration component, it not anticipated to affect any other target groups.</p>	
<p>Social Toolkit</p>	<p>The social sensing tool is a technology acceptance prediction system for border control technologies. The social sensing tool will analyze and estimate the activity and interactions between migrants/travelers, border staffs and border control technologies for technology acceptance prediction. The Social Toolkit Module is composed of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The socio-cultural framework; • Automated tools for assessing threshold <p>The socio-cultural framework module (SCFM) will allow the METICOS platform to assess the main reasons behind underlying circumstances that can affect the process of individuals with different sociocultural backgrounds trying to pass through given BCP technologies. It will make use of multiple parameters, such as</p>	<p>Yes: this component targets travellers and border staff), their interactions with the technology, response and waiting time while using technology and other relevant data attributes.</p>	<p>Yes: this component targets travellers and border staff), their interactions with the technology, response and waiting time while using technology and other relevant data attributes.</p>	

	<p>age, gender, social status, education, professional status, cultural background, lifestyle, native language, gestures etc.</p> <p>The Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) will define a specific threshold for each BCP technology when dealing with non-EU travellers. It will include parameters related to the overall complexity of the device/technology used, the level of interaction with different users, response time, the level of flexibility, level of support from border authorities etc., along with context-based data to adjust the threshold accordingly.</p>			
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From table 9, it derives that the target groups of the METICOS platform can be divided into two main categories: data subjects and recipients.

- The data subjects of the data processed by the METICOS platform are travellers and border staff about which data is being collected.
- The recipients of the data processed by the METICOS platform are: border staff members, researchers and decision-makers who are entitled to view the aggregated data via the Personnel Front-End and the Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit.

Consequently, in the METICOS' HRIA, the impacts on the human rights of travellers and border staff about which data is being collected should be analyzed. These two categories of target groups have already been sub-categorized in section 3.1.1.

3.2 Identification of impacted Human rights

Having now identified the target groups of both the border control technologies and the METICOS platform, this section is dedicated to identifying and listing the target groups' human rights which are potentially being impacted.

3.2.1 Human Rights that may be impacted by the border technologies

In order to identify and list the travellers' human rights which might potentially be impacted by the border control technologies envisaged to be evaluated, we proceeded to a horizon scanning of related European projects.

For each related European project, the table hereunder lists the impacted human rights which were identified in the ethical work that was carried out³⁵.

Table 10 - Horizon scanning of human rights impacted by border control technologies

Name and description of project	Identified impacted Human rights
<p>SMILE is a research project, based on biometric technologies, aimed to achieve an automated, rapid and highly secure self-service clearance process, such that increasing passenger throughput does not compromise border control reliability.</p> <p>A summary of the fundamental ethical concerns listing the impacted human rights is to be found</p>	<p>Human dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to the integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (Art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) – Equality before the law (Art. 20 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Respect cultural, religious and linguistic diversity (Art. 22 CFR) - Equality between men and women (Art. 23 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24 CFR) - Rights of the</p>

³⁵ In the table below, references are made to relevant articles of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (hereafter "CFR").

in “D8.6 - Ethics Manual and Guidelines for land BCPS” ³⁶ .	elderly (Art. 25 CFR) - Integration of persons with disabilities (Art. 26 CFR)
<p>PERSONA project provides a unified and tailored Impact Assessment Method for No-Gate Crossing Point Solutions capable of appropriately evaluating border controlling technologies and of ensuring that these solutions meet the requirements and expectations of governments, LEAS, and border crossing individuals.</p> <p>A summary of impacted human rights is to be found in “D1.3 - PERSONA benchmark for the assessment process”³⁷.</p>	Human dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Prohibition of inhuman or degrading treatment (Art. 4 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) - Protection in the event of removal, expulsion or extradition (Art. 19 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24) - Rights of the elderly (Art. 25 CFR) - Integration of persons with disabilities (Art. 26 CFR)
<p>TRESPASS aims to develop, demonstrate and validate a single cohesive risk-based border management concept for air, maritime and land border crossing points.</p> <p>TRESPASS identifies “ethical, legal and societal aspects” in “D9.6 - Typology of ethical, legal and societal issues of risk-based screening”³⁸. This document does not contain a comprehensive list of impacted human rights. Nonetheless, these could be deduced.</p>	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Right to good administration (Art. 41 CFR) - Right of access to documents (Art. 42 CFR) - Freedom of movement (Art. 45 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)
<p>MIRROR aims to produce technical tools to help assess the perceptions and misperceptions of Europe and individual European countries of persons migrating to Europe. By understanding these perceptions and misperceptions, it is hoped the border agencies can adopt a more predictive-oriented approach to their activities</p>	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to freedom of expression (Art. 11 CFR) - Right to freedom of Assembly and Association (Art. 12 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)

³⁶ SMILE, “D8.6 - Ethics Manual and Guidelines for land BCPS”, p.12, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5beee3af9&appId=PPGMS>

³⁷ PERSONA, “D1.3 - PERSONA benchmark for the assessment process”, p. 44, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5cef1ac5c&appId=PPGMS>

³⁸ TRESPASS, “D9.6 - Typology of ethical, legal and societal issues of risk-based screening”, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5d55dc0ec&appId=PPGMS>

<p>and manage migration flows, expectations, as well as their resources better.</p> <p>A summary of impacted human rights is to be found in “D3.2 - Human Rights Implications Checklist”³⁹.</p>	
<p>PROTECT develops a multimodal biometric solution for identity confirmation “on the move” of travellers with the aim to facilitate the Schengen Area external cross-border movements. The system should, therefore, process various “emerging” biometric modalities which could be processed in a contactless-way.</p> <p>A summary of impacted human rights is to be found in “D2.2 - Legal framework of biometric border control”⁴⁰.</p>	<p>Right to dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (Art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR), Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) - Protection in the event of removal, expulsion or extradition (Art. 19 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy (Art. 47 CFR).</p>

The human rights listed in table 10 might be impacted by border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform. These technologies are listed in tables 3 and 4. Most of these technologies share some common objectives: 1) they aim to confirm the identity of the holder of an eDocument through biometric verification and 2) they query border control databases to determine eligibility of border crossing according to the pre-defined rules.

By consequence, the main reasons explaining why these human rights are being impacted are:

- 1) the collection and processing of biometric data (facial image, fingerprints) to verify the identity of the document’s holder;
- 2) the processing of personal data in centralized IT systems (SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc) for border control management.

In the context of the METICOS platform, these legal impacts should be analysed since that the purpose of the platform is, amongst others, to measure the acceptance of border technologies by its users. However, social or technology acceptance differs from legal acceptability. As emphasized by the Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA), “Travellers’ attitudes towards technologies are an important element when assessing how new measures will be received. they can help authorities to forecast possible reactions and address existing fears or concerns. At the same time, travellers’ perceptions are only one element to take into account when assessing fundamental rights compliance of certain

³⁹ MIRROR, “D3.2 - Human Rights Implications Checklist”, p.18, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5d219840d&appId=PPGMS>

⁴⁰ PROTECT, “D2.2 - Legal framework of biometric border control”, p. 11, available at <https://emdesk.eu/shared/5ac3e931b9b0c-4bb5b487e91d73af0a5d898b3f898679>

measures. Violations of fundamental rights may occur regardless of whether the individual consents or not to a certain treatment, particularly in light of limited rights awareness”⁴¹.

Hence, within METICOS, the objective of the analysis of the human rights implications of border control technologies is to complement the social acceptance studies (conducted in WP5) in order to ensure that the collection of primary data through questionnaires as well as via the METICOS mobile & tablet applications reflect the human rights’ concerns deriving from the use of these technologies. The aim is to seek the views of the different target groups on a number of fundamental rights aspects related to the use of border control technologies.

3.2.2 Human Rights that may be impacted by the METICOS platform

In addition to the travellers’ human rights that may be impacted by the border technologies envisaged to be monitored, other human rights may be impacted by the big data tools and methods being used by the METICOS platform.

As a reminder, the purpose of the METICOS platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.

In order to fulfill its purpose, the METICOS platform processes different sets of data:

1. Primary Data: Primary data is the type of data that is collected directly from informed and consented “users” (travellers and border guards) during the METICOS project activities and during pilots at the Border Control Points. Such primary data originates from:
 - a. Questionnaires addressing specific questions about border crossing points, their control routines and technologies used;
 - b. Twitter: After crossing the border in the METICOS pilot site, the user is posting a tweet in the using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag;
 - c. METICOS Mobile Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a mobile application;
 - d. METICOS Tablet Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a tablet application.

⁴¹ FRA, Survey in the framework of the eu-LISA pilot on smart borders – travellers’ views on and experiences of smart borders, Smart borders pilot final report - annexes, November 2015, p.307, available at https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/what-we-do/policies/borders-and-visas/smart-borders/docs/smart_borders_pilot_-_technical_report_annexes_en.pdf

2. Secondary data: Secondary data is the type of data that is relevant to METICOS, but has been collected in the past. Such data is already available to use in the context of the project from existing sources. Such secondary data originates from:
 - a. Statistical data originating from border crossing points' databases;
 - b. Twitter: The aim is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.
 - c. Online reviews of BCPs on blogs/websites

By consequence of these data processing operations, the main human rights that might be potentially impacted by the METICOS platform are the rights to privacy (art. 7 CFR) and to data protection (art. 8 CFR). Given the importance of the rights to privacy and data protection for the METICOS platform, a specific Deliverable (D3.1) was dedicated to conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). A DPIA is “a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR. In other words, a DPIA is a process for building and demonstrating compliance.”⁴²

Given the work that has been carried out in the DPIA, the aim of this HRIA is not to duplicate the work conducted in D3.1 by analysing the impacts of the METICOS platform on the rights to privacy and data protection. However, as these two rights are essential to the free development of an individual's personality and identity, these rights also facilitate the enjoyment of other human rights⁴³. By consequence, any breach of privacy or data protection requirements identified in D3.1 might also have consequences on other human rights such as freedom of speech, freedom of thought, freedom of movement, prohibition of discrimination, right to liberty, conscience and religion, etc.

Moreover, at this stage of the project, we identified that other human rights may be impacted by the METICOS platform as a consequence of:

- 1) The potential use of Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) during pilots in order to detect the participants' acceptance;
- 2) The potential collection of data from participants' travel documents;
- 3) The potential connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc;

⁴² See Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP 248 rev.01, adopted on 4 April 2017, last revised and adopted on 4 October 2017

⁴³ The General Assembly, the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights and special procedure mandate holders have recognised privacy as a gateway to the enjoyment of other rights (UNGA resolution 68/167, A/HRC/13/37; Human Rights Council resolution 20/8).

The table 11 below lists which human rights may be impacted by the METICOS platform. Additional impacts on human rights might be identified or detailed at a later stage of the METICOS project (for example, during the review or audit stage defined in section 6). In such event, this will be reported in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”, due on M30.

Table 11 - Identified human right impacts of the METICOS platform

Origin of the impact	Human right(s) being impacted	Explanation
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the travellers’ data within the METICOS platform such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deanonimization of the primary and secondary data being processed by the METICOS platform. • Illegitimate access to primary and secondary data processed by the METICOS platform. 	<p>Human dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to the integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Prohibition of inhuman or degrading treatment (Art. 4 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Freedom of thought, conscience and religion (art. 10 CFR) - Freedom of expression and information (art. 11 CFR) - Equality before the law (Art. 20 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Respect cultural, religious and linguistic diversity (Art. 22 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)</p>	<p>In case of data breaches in the METICOS platform, illegitimate recipients might take unfair individual decisions towards METICOS users. Such decisions might impact different human rights, depending on the concrete circumstances.</p>
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the border guard staff’s data within the METICOS platform.</p>	<p>Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Freedom to choose an occupation and right to engage in work (Art. 15 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR)</p>	<p>In case of breaches of border guard’s data in the METICOS platform, the staff may be discriminated by their employers.</p>
<p>Potential use of Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) during pilots in order to detect the travellers’ acceptance.</p>	<p>Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR)</p>	<p>Using Facial Emotion Recognition cameras during the pilots might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.</p>

The potential collection of data from the travellers' documents by non-authorized border staff ⁴⁴ .	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR)	The collection of data directly from travel documents by non-authorized border staff might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.
The potential connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, etc ⁴⁵ .	Right to the integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (Art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) - Protection in the event of removal, expulsion or extradition (Art. 19 CFR) - Freedom of movement (Art. 45 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)	The connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, etc might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such interferences might have impacts on other fundamental rights depending on the concrete circumstances.
Lack of transparency of the data collection from Twitter and other social media.	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Freedom of expression and information (art. 11 CFR).	Retrieving any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and mining the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such a data processing could also potentially lead to an interference with the freedom of expression.
Potential undercoverage bias due to target groups not adequately	Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) – Equality before the law (Art. 20 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art.	The research results of the METICOS project might be biased in case of insufficient

⁴⁴ As explained in section 5, because of the ethical risks, it was decided to finally not collect data directly from travel documents.

⁴⁵ As explained in section 5, because of the ethical risks, it was decided to finally not connect the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES.

represented in the METICOS pilots' and research' samples.	21 CFR) - Respect cultural, religious and linguistic diversity (Art. 22 CFR) - Equality between men and women (Art. 23 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24 CFR) - Rights of the elderly (Art. 25 CFR) - Integration of persons with disabilities (Art. 26 CFR)	representation of the different impacted groups of persons identified in section 3. Such biases might have impacts on different human rights depending on the concrete circumstances.
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4 Evaluation of the impacts on human rights

4.1 Evaluation of impacts on human rights deriving from border control technologies

Within METICOS, the objective of the analysis of the human rights' implications of border control technologies is to complement the social acceptance studies (conducted in WP5) in order to ensure that the collection of primary data through questionnaires as well as via the METICOS mobile & tablet applications reflect the human rights' concerns deriving from the use of these technologies. The aim is to seek the views of the different target groups on a number of fundamental rights aspects related to the use of border control technologies.

4.1.1 Impact of the processing of biometric data in travel documents

4.1.1.1 Description of the types of biometrics included in travel documents

According to the Article 29 Working Party, "Biometric data changes irrevocably the relation between body and identity, because they make the characteristics of the human body 'machine-readable' and subject to further use"⁴⁶. This is the main reason justifying that biometric data is considered as being particularly sensitive by EU data protection norms⁴⁷.

Over the years, border control has become smarter with eDocuments using biometric technology as a key element, enabling authorities to verify that a traveller is who they claim to be and that they are authorised to enter a country.

The table 12 below lists the type of biometrics contained in each type of travel document as well as the categories of persons that are exempted from providing fingerprints.

Table 12 - Types of biometrics included in eDocuments and exemptions

Type of eDocument	Biometrics included	Exempted persons
ID card ⁴⁸	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facial image two fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children under the age of 12 years may be exempt from

⁴⁶ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 3/2012 on developments in biometric technologies, adopted on 27th April 2012, WP193, p.4.

⁴⁷ See article 9 of the GDPR and article 10 of the Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA.

⁴⁸ The inclusion of biometrics in ID cards is regulated by article 3 of Regulation (EU) 2019/1157 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on strengthening the security of identity cards of Union citizens and of residence documents issued to Union citizens and their family members exercising their right of free movement.

		<p>the requirement to give fingerprints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 6 years shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints. • Persons in respect of whom fingerprinting is physically impossible shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints⁴⁹.
ePassport ⁵⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facial image • Two fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 12 years are exempted to provide fingerprints. • Persons, where fingerprinting is physically impossible are exempted⁵¹.
Residence permit ⁵²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facial image • Two Fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The capture of fingerprints is compulsory as of six years of age. • Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically impossible are exempted.
Schengen Visa ⁵³	The visa stickers do not contain any biometric traits. However, once an application is found	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 12 are exempted to provide fingerprints.

⁴⁹ According to article 4, §3 of Regulation (EU) 2019/1157, “Member States shall issue an identity card having a validity of 12 months or less where it is temporarily physically impossible to take fingerprints of any of the fingers of the applicant”.

⁵⁰ The inclusion of biometrics in ePassports is regulated by article 1 of the consolidated version of Council regulation No 2252/2004 of 13 December 2004 on standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States.

⁵¹ According to article 2b of the consolidated version of Council regulation No 2252/2004: “Where fingerprinting of the designated fingers is temporarily impossible, Member States shall allow the fingerprinting of the other fingers. Where it is also temporarily impossible to take fingerprints of any of the other fingers, they may issue a temporary passport having a validity of 12 months or less”.

⁵² The inclusion of biometrics in residence permits is regulated by articles 4a and 4b of the consolidated version of Council Regulation (EC) No 1030/2002 of 13 June 2002 laying down a uniform format for residence permits for third-country nationals.

⁵³ The inclusion of biometrics in the VIS is regulated by article 13 of the consolidated version of Regulation (EC) No 810/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a Community Code on Visas (Visa Code).

	admissible as set out in the Visa Code, the visa authority creates the application file by entering data into the Visa Information System (VIS) including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facial image⁵⁴ • 10 fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically impossible are exempted. If the fingerprinting of fewer than 10 fingers is possible, the maximum number of fingerprints shall be taken.
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As illustrated in the table above, the type of biometrics included in the majority of the EU travel documents consist into two fingerprints and the holder's facial image. The use of these biometrics could impact significantly on the dignity, privacy and the right to data protection of vulnerable people such as young children, elderly people and persons physically unable to complete the enrolment process successfully. This is why regulatory texts contain some exemptions as regards the requirement to provide fingerprints. Indeed, appropriate safeguards must be in place against the risks of stigmatization or discrimination of those individuals either because of their age or because of their inability to enrol. In any case, "specific safeguards (such as appropriate fall-back procedures) should be implemented so as to ensure the respect for human dignity and fundamental freedoms of any individual that is unable to complete the enrolment process successfully and thereby avoid burdening such individual with the imperfections of the technical system"⁵⁵.

Moreover, factors such as class, ability, gender, skin colour and age – and the intersection of these factors – can negatively influence someone's ability to be recognized by the biometric apparatus.

In addition, for all categories of persons, there are privacy risks that should be taken into account when relying on fingerprints and facial recognition. These risks are summarized in the next two sub-sections.

4.1.1.2 Main privacy risks of fingerprints

Fingerprint recognition is among the oldest and most widely studied and most extensively deployed biometric systems. Identification by fingerprints has been used for more than 100 years in law enforcement for both verification and identification tasks. It is founded in the fact that every individual has unique fingerprints showing specific characteristics that can be measured in order to decide if a fingerprint matches against an enrolled sample. Enrolment requires the individual to be physically present as well as, depending on the expected use, well trained personnel in order to ensure good

⁵⁴ Although the VIS does not collect facial images at the moment, the Council has proposed an amendment for the proposed VIS Regulation suggesting that the visa procedure and the VIS should benefit from the technology developments related to facial image recognition and taking live facial images as part of the short stay visa procedure. See Council of the European Union, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EC) No 767/2008, Regulation (EC) No 810/2009, Regulation (EU) 2017/2226, Regulation (EU) 2016/399, Regulation XX/2018 [Interoperability Regulation], and Decision 2004/512/EC and repealing Council Decision 2008/633/JHA— Presidency compromise proposals regarding the recitals, 13799/18, 5 November 2018.

⁵⁵ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 3/2012 on developments in biometric technologies, adopted on 27th April 2012, WP193, p.15.

data quality. Fingerprint capture is not a trivial task. In that sense matching accuracy will depend on the image quality in relation to the image technique. Even not being in principle a highly invasive method, it can be felt as such because it comes with the negative image of being treated as a suspect due to its common use in law enforcement.

According to the Article 29 Working Party⁵⁶, there are data protection concerns associated with the use of fingerprints that can be briefly described as follows:

- **Accuracy:** Even though fingerprints eventually present a high accuracy rate, this can be challenged due to limitations related to the information (low quality of the data or non-consistent acquisition process) or representation (features selected or quality of the extraction algorithms) issues. This can lead to false rejection or false matches.
- **Impact:** The irreversibility of the process can reduce the possibility of the individual of exercising their rights or to reverse decisions adopted based on a false identification. The reliance on the accuracy of fingerprinting can make possible mistakes harder to rectify, leading to far reaching consequences for individuals. This needs to be taken into account when the proportionality of the processing in relation to the specific decision to be taken based on the fingerprints is assessed. It should be also mentioned that lack of security measures can lead to identity theft that can have a strong impact for the individual.
- **Linkability:** fingerprints provide potential for misuse as the data can be linked with other databases. This possibility of linking up to other databases can lead to uses non compatible with the original purposes.
- **Processing of sensitive data:** According to some studies, fingerprint images can reveal ethnical information of the individual.
- **Further purposes or purposes of processing:** Central storage of data, especially on large databases, implies risks associated with data security, linkability and function creep. This allows, in absence of safeguards, the use of the fingerprints for purposes different than those that initially justified the processing.
- **Revocability:** fingerprint data are very stable with time and should be considered irrevocable. A fingerprint template may be revoked under certain conditions.

4.1.1.3 Main privacy risks of facial image

The face, like fingerprints, has been used extensively as a source of biometric data for a number of years. More recently it is not only identity that can be determined from a face but physiological and psychological characteristics such as ethnic origin, emotion and wellbeing.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, pp.20-21.

The ability to extract this volume of data from an image and the fact that a photograph can be taken from some distance without the knowledge of the data subject demonstrates the level of data protection issues which can arise from such technologies.

According to the Article 29 Working Party⁵⁷, data protection risks associated with the use of facial recognition systems can be described as follows:

- **Accuracy:** If the quality of images cannot be guaranteed there is a risk that the accuracy will be compromised. If a face is not captured (obscured by hair or a hat) it is clear that a matching or categorisation cannot take place without a high degree of error. Pose and illumination variations remain a big challenge for facial recognition, highly affecting the accuracy.
- **Consent & Transparency:** A data protection risk not seen in many other types of biometric data processing is the fact that images can be captured and processed from a range of viewpoints, environmental conditions and without the knowledge of the data subject.
- **Further purpose or purposes of processing:** Once captured, whether legitimately or unlawfully, digital images can be easily shared or copied for processing in different systems from those which they were originally intended.
- **Processing of sensitive data:** Processing of biometric data could be used to determine sensitive data, in particular those with visual cues such as race, ethnic group or perhaps a medical condition.

4.1.1.4 Dealing with the impact of biometrics in travel documents within METICOS

Within METICOS, in order to reflect the human rights' concerns deriving from the use of biometrics in travel documents, it is recommended to:

- Involve participants holding the different types of travel documents listed in table 12 during the METICOS pilots. This might be achieved by involving the target groups identified in table 7 of this Deliverable.
- Involve participants of different:
 - a) age-groups, including elderly (children will not be involved in the pilots but a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns, for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 – see section 6);
 - b) gender;
 - c) race /ethnicity;
 - d) nationality;
 - e) religious philosophical beliefs

⁵⁷ Ibid., pp. 22-23..

- f) health condition, in particular disabilities.

This might be achieved by involving the target groups being identified in table 8 of this Deliverable.

- In the questionnaires being circulated (as well as in the questions asked via the METICOS mobile and tablet applications), it is recommended to include questions such as:
 - Do you believe that the storage of biometrics in travel documents is humiliating (intrusive to your dignity)?
 - Do you believe that the storage of biometrics in travel documents is intrusive to your privacy?
 - Do you believe it is important to be informed on why your biometric identifiers are stored on travel documents?
 - Do you consider that the storage of the facial image on travel documents is important to secure borders?
 - Do you consider is the storage of fingerprints in travel documents is important to secure borders?
 - How comfortable do you feel with facial image being stored in travel documents?
 - How comfortable do you feel with fingerprints being stored in travel documents?
 - Which biometrics are you more in favour of to be stored in travel documents (facial image or fingerprints)?
 - Would you prefer travel documents not to contain any biometrics?
 - For fingerprints, how many fingers' templates do you consider proportionate to be stored on travel documents?
 - Do you trust the reliability of the fingerprints stored on your travel document?
 - Do you trust the reliability of the facial image stored on your travel document?
 - Do you believe that biometrics are securely stored in travel documents?
 - Under what age do you consider that fingerprints should not be stored on travel documents?
 - Under what age do you consider that facial image should not be stored on travel documents?
 - Do you believe that the storage of the facial image is discriminatory on grounds of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation?
 - Do you believe that the storage of the fingerprints is discriminatory on grounds of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation?

The aim of this recommendation is not to provide a final list of questions to be included in the questionnaires. This draft list is only a first tentative to lay a basis for discussion during the review stage's workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 – see section 6.

- If the questionnaires being circulated (as well as the questions asked via the METICOS mobile and tablet applications) aim to evaluate the acceptance of iris recognition, it should be recalled to the respondents that iris is not a type of biometrics being currently allowed to be stored in

eDocuments according to applicable regulations. This remark is also valid for any questions related to the user’s acceptance of other types of biometrics than facial image and fingerprints.

4.1.2 Impact of the use of large-scale IT systems

4.1.2.1 Description of the EU large-scale IT systems

The large-scale EU large-scale databases presently include: the second-generation Schengen Information System (SIS II), the Visa Information System (VIS), the European Dactyloscopy (Eurodac), and the more recent Entry-Exit System (EES), European Criminal Records Information System for Third Country Nationals (ECRIS-TCN) and European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS).

In a nutshell, “the SIS allows competent authorities in the EU to issue and consult alerts on missing or wanted objects and people. The VIS supports Member States’ consular authorities in the management of applications for short-stay visas to visit or to transit through the Schengen Area. The Eurodac supports competent authorities in determining the responsibility for examining an asylum application. In the near future, the EES will electronically register the time and place of entry and exit of third-country nationals, both those requiring a visa and those who are visa-exempt, admitted for a short stay, other than those refused to entry. The ECRIS-TCN will allow Member States’ authorities to identify which other Member States hold criminal records on the third-country nationals or stateless persons being checked. The ETIAS will constitute a pre-travel authorisation system for visa-exempt travellers, the key function of which is to verify if a third-country national meets entry requirements before travelling to the Schengen Area, enabling pre-travel assessment of irregular migration, security or public health risks”⁵⁸.

The table 13 below lists the types of biometrics being processed in each large-scale IT system as well as the persons being exempted, when applicable.

Table 13 - Type of biometrics included in each large-scale IT system

IT database	Biometrics included	Exempted persons
SIS	Palm prints, fingerprints, facial images and DNA samples.	N/A
VIS	Facial image ⁵⁹ and data relating to the five fingerprints of the index, middle finger, ring finger, little	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children under the age of 12 are exempted to provide fingerprints.

⁵⁸ J. P. Burges and D. Kloza, “Border control and new technologies – addressing Integrated Impact Assessment”, 2021, p. 121.

⁵⁹ Although the VIS does not collect facial images at the moment, the Council has proposed an amendment for the proposed VIS Regulation suggesting that the visa procedure and the VIS should benefit from the technology developments related to facial image recognition and taking live facial images as part of the short stay visa procedure. See Council of the European Union, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EC) No 767/2008, Regulation (EC) No 810/2009, Regulation (EU) 2017/2226, Regulation (EU) 2016/399, Regulation XX/2018 [Interoperability Regulation], and Decision 2004/512/EC and

	finger and the thumb from the right hand and, where present, from the left hand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically impossible. If the fingerprinting of fewer than 10 fingers is possible, the maximum number of fingerprints shall be taken.
EES	Facial image and data relating to the four fingerprints of the index, middle finger, ring finger and little finger from the right hand where present, and otherwise from the left hand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children under the age of 12 shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints. Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically impossible shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints.
Eurodac	<p>Data relating to fingerprints of all or at least the index fingers, and if those are missing, the prints of all other fingers of a person, or a latent fingerprint.</p> <p>The recently amended Eurodac proposal released in September 2020 proposes to add the facial image⁶⁰.</p>	<p>Each Member State shall promptly take the fingerprints of all fingers of every third-country national or stateless person of at least 14 years of age who is apprehended by the competent control authorities in connection with the irregular crossing.</p> <p>Where it is not possible to take the fingerprints of the apprehended person on account of measures taken to ensure his or her health or the protection of public health, the Member State concerned shall take and send such fingerprints as soon as possible and no later than 48 hours after those health grounds no longer prevail.</p>

repealing Council Decision 2008/633/JHA— Presidency compromise proposals regarding the recitals, 13799/18, 5 November 2018.

⁶⁰ Amended proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the establishment of 'Eurodac' for the comparison of biometric data for the effective application of Regulation (EU) XXX/XXX [Regulation on Asylum and Migration Management] and of Regulation (EU) XXX/XXX [Resettlement Regulation], for identifying an illegally staying third-country national or stateless person and on requests for the comparison with Eurodac data by Member States' law enforcement authorities and Europol for law enforcement purposes and amending Regulations (EU) 2018/1240 and (EU) 2019/818.

		The recently amended Eurodac proposal released in September 2020 proposes to lower the age for biometric data collection from 14 to 6 years old ⁶¹ .
ECRIS-TCN	Facial image and the data relating to plain and rolled impressions of the fingerprints of each of a person's fingers.	N/A
ETIAS	No biometrics	N/A

These six systems have key similarities in common; namely, that they primarily—but not exclusively—relate to third-country nationals and that most of them collect biometric data⁶².

As established in the figure 14 below, some of them were created for border management purposes, whereas others were originally built for security purposes.

Figure 3 - Main purposes of the six IT large-scale systems

For border and law enforcement authorities, one of the problems of having numerous information systems is that end-users have to visit so many databases from which they will receive overlapping and delayed information⁶³. Therefore, the Interoperability Regulations⁶⁴ were adopted in order to (a) increase the effectiveness of border checks, (b) help to prevent and combat irregular migration, (c)

⁶¹ Ibidem.

⁶² C. Blasi Casagran, Fundamental Rights Implications of Interconnecting Migration and Policing Databases in the EU, Human Rights Law Review, 2021, p.2.

⁶³ Ibid., p.5.

⁶⁴ Regulation (EU) 2019/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2019 on establishing a framework for interoperability between EU information systems in the field of borders and visa and amending Regulations (EC) No 767/2008, (EU) 2016/399, (EU) 2017/2226, (EU) 2018/1240, (EU) 2018/1726 and (EU) 2018/1861 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Decisions 2004/512/EC and 2008/633/JHA and Regulation (EU) 2019/818 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2019 on establishing a framework for interoperability between EU information systems in the field of police and judicial cooperation, asylum and migration and amending Regulations (EU) 2018/1726, (EU) 2018/1862 and (EU) 2019/816.

reinforce the level of security within the EU, (d) promote the implementation of the common visa policy, (e) detect, prevent and investigate terrorist and other serious crimes and (f) help identify unknown and undocumented persons.

To achieve these objectives, the six above-mentioned large-scale databases are merged and crosschecked through four new components: The European search portal (ESP), the shared biometric matching service (BMS), the common identity repository (CIR) and the multiple-identity detector (MID).

Each of these four interoperability components has been created for a specific purpose:

- The ESP will enable the searching of alphanumeric or biometric data through the six databases, plus Interpol and Europol data;
- The shared BMS will extract biometric ‘templates’ from each of the six EU databases with the purpose of facilitating the searching and cross-matching of the biometric data;
- The CIR will store the biometric and biographic data of non-EU nationals, collected via Eurodac, the VIS, EES, ETIAS and ECRIS-TCN;
- The MID will make “identity confirmation files” whenever a new file is created or updated in the EES, VIS or ETIAS, and an alert on a person is created or updated in the SIS, or a new record is created or modified in the ECRIS-TCN. The MID will store links between the individuals present in more than one of these systems, and these links will be labelled in four categories: white, yellow, green and red.

4.1.2.2 Impacts of large-scale IT systems on human rights

The EU large-scale IT systems as merged by the Interoperability Regulations may have negative implications on different human rights.

1. **Data protection and privacy:** One of the central fundamental rights questions of the Interoperability Regulations relates to the principle of purpose limitation. The regulations blur partly the boundaries between migration management and the fight against (serious) crime and terrorism⁶⁵. “Differences based on national origin are in essence the purpose for adopting the Interoperability Regulations, as they incorporate additional security checks for third-country nationals, allowing a differentiated treatment between EU citizens and third-country nationals. The new Regulations place in the same box short-stay travellers, migrants, asylum seekers, irregular migrants and criminals, having only one thing in common: they are third-country nationals. No connection whatsoever to an illegal behaviour will be considered when collecting their data. Thus, this system seems to be based on the (wrong) idea that non-EU nationals are more likely than EU nationals to be engaged in activities threatening public,

⁶⁵ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, “Interoperability and fundamental rights implications”, FRA Opinion – 1/2018, p.10.

bringing closer the controversial concept of ‘pre-crime’. It certainly creates an unjustified difference of treatment between EU citizens and third-country nationals”⁶⁶.

2. **Equality before the law and non-discrimination:** “Interoperability can lead to differentiated treatment of people based on their sex, race, colour, disability or other grounds prohibited by the non-discrimination clause in Article 21 of the Charter. [...] The risk of discrimination is highest with the Multiple Identity Detector, which needs to be carefully assessed from different perspectives. The first one relates to sex. Women more frequently change their last name than men. In many countries, when a woman marries she takes on the family name of her husband. A woman who is in an IT system with her premarriage name and travels again will feature as a person having two different identities. The impact of the change of surname will depend on how sophisticated the algorithm for the automatic verification of multiple identity is. Nevertheless, statistically, women will remain more likely to be stopped at first entry compared to men (for example, where in addition to their surname other pieces of information such as passport details following a renewal of the document do not match) with the risk of missing connecting flights or other important commitments. This risk is higher where biometrics are not used, as is the case in ETIAS and partly in SIS, as searchable biometrics are only now gradually being introduced in SIS. Also other groups of individuals – for example people from societies where certain names are very frequent (e.g. Mr/Ms Lee; Mohammed; etc.) – are likely to face more problems than others when their identities are verified. [...] Persons who as a reflection of their social origin make mistakes when they complete an ETIAS request from their homes are one category who is likely to face more problems. [...] The risk of unfavourable treatment may also originate from an unreliable biometric match. In case of facial recognition, phenotypical origin – thus the colour of the skin – plays also a role, as white skin reflects light more than dark skin and not enough illumination for very dark skin may result in false match”⁶⁷.
3. **Special attention for certain categories of people:** “Next to non-discrimination, interoperability may bring unforeseen negative consequences for children, older persons and persons with disabilities. Persons with disabilities enjoy the “freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas on an equal basis with others and through all forms of communication of their choice”, in line with Article 21 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. The fact that they are not able to provide fingerprints making thus a comparison based on biometrics not possible, should not result in disadvantageous treatment. The reliability of a fingerprint (but also a facial image) match decreases when fingerprints taken at a young age are compared many years after the time they were collected. With age fingertips also deteriorate which may affect the reliability of a match”⁶⁸.

⁶⁶ C. Blasi Casagran, op.cit, p.21.

⁶⁷ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, “Interoperability and fundamental rights implications”, op. cit., pp. 13-14.

⁶⁸ Ibid., p.14.

4. **Impacts on other human rights:** Negative consequences on other human rights might derive from “mistakes in the system and in the automated processing of personal data can have on an individual. For example, when the system fails to recognize an individual or if the extension of a visa is not included in the database, a person might be denied entry into an EU Member State or, in the worst case, run the risk of being apprehended and detained. The person affected may face difficulties to prove that he/she really is the person he/she claims to be. In the case of third-country nationals travelling to the EU, this vulnerability might be compounded by language problems. Many problems could occur, for example data errors, but also fraud and forgery of biometric data and incorrect or not up to date personal data included in the IT system. The most likely implication of incorrect data in the Entry Exit system concern the risks of persons mistakenly flagged as over-stayers and the use that police, immigration or other officials may make of such information”⁶⁹. A last non-negligible negative consequence is, when applicable, the relative difficulty to exercise the rights to access, rectification or erasure of personal data being processed in EU-large scale databases.

4.1.2.3 *Dealing with the impact of the use of large-scale IT systems within METICOS*

Within METICOS, in order to reflect the human rights’ concerns deriving from the use of large-scale IT systems, it is recommended to:

- Involve participants of which personal data is being processed by the different EU-large scale databases listed in table 13. This might be achieved by involving the target groups identified in table 7 of this Deliverable.
- Involve participants of different:
 - a) age-groups, including elderly (children will not be involved in the pilots but a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns, for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 – see section 6);
 - b) language;
 - c) gender;
 - d) race /ethnicity;
 - e) Nationality;
 - f) religious philosophical beliefs;
 - g) health condition, in particular disabilities;
 - h) Sexual orientation.

This might be achieved by involving the target groups being identified in table 8 of this Deliverable.

⁶⁹ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, “FRA survey in the framework of the eu-LISA pilot on smart borders – travellers’ views on and experiences of smart borders”, in Smart Borders Pilot Project Technical Report Annexes, Volume 2, 2015, p. 308.

- In the questionnaires being circulated (as well as in the questions asked via the METICOS mobile and tablet applications), it is recommended to include questions such as:
 - Do you believe that the processing of biometric data in EU large-scale databases is humiliating (intrusive to your dignity)?
 - Do you believe that the processing of biometric data in EU large-scale databases is intrusive to your privacy?
 - Do you believe it is important to be informed on why biometric identifiers are processed in several EU large-scale databases?
 - Do you consider that the processing of the facial image in EU large-scale databases is important to secure borders?
 - Do you consider that the processing of fingerprints in EU large-scale databases is important to secure borders?
 - How comfortable do you feel with facial image being processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - How comfortable do you feel with fingerprints being processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Which biometrics are you more in favour of to be processed in EU large scale databases (facial image or fingerprints)?
 - Would you prefer EU large-scale databases not to contain any biometrics?
 - Do you trust the accuracy and reliability of the information (both alphanumeric and biometric) processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Do you believe that personal data are securely stored in EU large scale databases?
 - Would you have problems with the police accessing your biometric data in EU large scale databases ?
 - Do you believe that the processing of information (both alphanumeric and biometric) is discriminatory on grounds of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation?
 - Under what age do you consider that fingerprints should not be processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Under what age do you consider that facial image should not be processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Do you believe that personal data processed in EU large scale databases can be easily corrected in case of mistakes?
 - Do you believe that automated systems would cause more or less discrimination compared to checks done by border guards?

The aim of this recommendation is not to provide a final list of questions to be included in the questionnaires. This draft list is only a first tentative to lay a basis for discussion during the review stage's workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 – see section 6.

- During the review stage's workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 (see section 6) to identify and discuss any further human rights' concerns

deriving from the use of the six main EU large-scale databases as well as from the interoperability framework.

4.2 Evaluation of impacts on human rights deriving from the METICOS platform

This section analyses the impacts on human rights of the data processing operations that are/were envisaged to be conducted by the METICOS platform in order to measure the users' acceptance and the efficiency of border control technologies.

4.2.1 Impact of Facial Emotion Recognition

During early discussions within the METICOS consortium, it was considered to use cameras with facial emotion recognition as a primary data source for the METICOS platform. The aim was to use such technology to analyze facial expressions of travellers (and participants during the pilots) in order to measure their acceptance of border control technologies. After ethical examination, this option was discarded for the reasons mentioned in this sub-section.

4.2.1.1 Risks of using facial emotion recognition

The EDPS defines "Facial Emotion Recognition" (hereafter "FER") as being "a technology used for analysing sentiments by different sources, such as pictures and videos. It belongs to the family of technologies often referred to as "affective computing", a multidisciplinary field of research on computer's capabilities to recognise and interpret human emotions and affective states and it often builds on Artificial Intelligence technologies"⁷⁰.

The supervisory body considers that the complexity of facial expressions, the potential use of the technology in any context, and the involvement of new technologies such as artificial intelligence raise significant privacy and data protection risks:

- A first risk is non-proportionality: "Turning human expressions into a data source to infer emotions touches clearly a part of peoples' most private data. Being a disruptive technology, FER raises important issues regarding necessity and proportionality. It has to be carefully assessed, whether deploying FER is indeed necessary for achieving the pursued objectives or whether there is a less intrusive alternative"⁷¹.
- A second risk is the lack of data accuracy: "Analysis of emotions based on facial expressions may not be accurate, as facial expressions can slightly vary among individuals, may mix different emotional states experienced at the same time (e.g. fear and anger, happy and sad) or may not express an emotion at all. On the other hand, there are emotions that may not be expressed on someone's face, thus inference based solely on facial expression may lead to wrong impressions. Additional factors can add to the ambiguity of the facial expressions, such as contextual clauses (sarcasm), and socio-cultural context. In addition, technical aspects

⁷⁰EDPS, TechDispatch #1/2021 - Facial Emotion Recognition, May 2021, available at https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/publications/techdispatch/techdispatch-12021-facial-emotion-recognition_en

⁷¹ Ibidem.

(different angles of the camera, lighting conditions and masking several parts of the face) can affect the quality of a captured facial expression. Furthermore, even in the case of accurate recognition of emotions, the use of the results may lead to wrong inferences about a person, as FER does not explain the trigger of emotions, which may be a thought of a recent or past event”⁷².

- A third risk is a lack of fairness: “The accuracy of the facial emotion algorithm results can play an important role in discriminating on grounds of skin colour or ethnic origin. Societal norms and cultural differences have been found to influence the level of expression of some emotions while some algorithms have been found to be biased against several groups, based on skin colour. For instance, a study testing algorithms of facial emotion recognition revealed they assigned more negative emotions (anger) to faces of persons of African descent than to other faces. Furthermore, whenever there was ambiguity, the former were scored as angrier”⁷³.
- A fourth risk is a lack of transparency and control: “Where the data subjects’ facial expressions are captured in a remote manner, it may not be clear to them which system or application will process their data, for which purposes, and who the controllers are. As a result, they would not be in the position to freely give consent or exercise control over the processing of their personal data, including sharing with third-parties. Where data subjects are not provided with accurate information, access and control over the use of FER, they are deprived of their freedom to select which aspects of their life can be used to affect other contexts (e.g. emotions in social interactions could be used in the context of recruitment). [...] Another consequence of the remote capture of facial expressions and the obscurity of their processing is that data subjects might not be provided with information on which other sources of data these will be aggregated to. Also, advanced AI algorithms add to the complexity of transparency needs, as they may detect slight movements of facial muscle that are unconscious even for the individuals. This would contribute to the unpleasant feeling of vulnerability due to unwanted exposure”⁷⁴.
- A fifth risk is related to the processing of special categories of personal data: “FER technology can detect the existence, changes or total lack of facial expressions, and link this to an emotional state. As a result, in some contexts, algorithms may infer special categories of personal data, such as political opinions or health data. [...] Also, by the lack of facial expressions, algorithms are able to detect signs of alexithymia, a state in which one cannot understand the feelings they experience or lack the words to describe these feelings. This finding can be linked to severe psychiatric and neurological disorders, such as psychosis. Furthermore, analysis of historical data on one’s emotional state may reveal other health conditions such as depression”⁷⁵.

⁷² Ibidem.

⁷³ Ibidem.

⁷⁴ Ibidem.

⁷⁵ Ibidem.

- The last identified risk is related to profiling and automated decision-making: “FER technology could be used for purposes of safeguarding public security, for instance at concerts, sport events or airports, to quickly identify signs of aggression and stress and identify potential terrorists. However, if such an identification was based solely on FER and was not combined with other actions or triggers that this person is dangerous, this could introduce further risks for the data subjects. For instance, a person could be subject to unjustified delays to perform further security checks or investigations, causing them to miss participation in an event, boarding on a flight or even lead to unjustified arrest”⁷⁶.

4.2.1.2 Dealing with the impact of Facial Emotion Recognition within METICOS

Within METICOS, in order to reflect the human rights’ concerns deriving from the use of facial emotion recognition, it is recommended to:

- Not to use to use cameras with facial emotion recognition as a primary data source for the METICOS platform. At this stage of the project, it is considered that the use of cameras for behavior & emotion detection could potentially lead to a “function creep”. This means that such data might have been used by border control authorities beyond the limits of the research purposes in order to support measures or decisions taken with regard to travelers (profiling/risk management/etc.). As a reminder, the purpose of the METICOS platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions. The use of facial emotion recognition cameras could have led to the processing of data beyond the scope of the project by providing end-users with data permitting individual (and real-time) decisions that could provoke negative consequences for travelers (for example, further security checks without legal justification in the Border Schengen Code).
- As an alternative to the use of FER, to analyze further the possibility and relevance of collecting data via “traditional” cameras (or physical presence of researchers) on the basis of the informed consent of pilot participants. Such an additional source of data might provide interesting information about the concrete interaction of travellers with border control technologies.

4.2.2 Impact of collecting data from official border control databases and travel documents

As reminded in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”, article 5, §1, c) of the General Data Protection Regulation imposes personal data to be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed”.

⁷⁶ Ibidem.

The principle of “data minimization” means that a data controller should limit the collection of personal information to what is directly relevant and necessary to accomplish a specified purpose. In other words, data controllers should collect only the personal data they really need to pursue their aim.

In the context of METICOS, the purpose of the platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions. Given this specified purpose, it was decided:

- Not to collect data from travel documents. It was considered that it is not necessary for the purposes of the METICOS project to collect information enabling the individualization of each traveler/border control staff member (first name, last name, date of birth, etc.). Indeed, for the purposes of the project, it is only necessary to collect some generic demographic data (Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Frequent Flyer, Travel Habits/Experience, Level of Education, Sex, Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background/Orientation, Trust in BC Authorities, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence + Current occupation, Current work status [employed-unemployed-self-employed], per traveler or Rank, Work Experience, per staff member). Such demographic data is collected via the METICOS Mobile Application, the METICOS Tablet Application and Questionnaires. This alternative also offers more transparency during the data collection.
- Not to collect personal data from Border Control Databases such as VIS, SIS, EES, ETIAS, etc. It was considered that such extremely sensitive data were absolutely not needed for the purposes of the project.
- Not to collect data from biometric sensors (e-gates, scanners, etc.) at border crossing points. It was considered that such data collection is not needed for the purposes of the project. Instead, it was decided that obtaining statistics about their use was sufficient (Number of access attempts with documents not accepted by the system; Number of access attempts with non-eligible documents; Number of complaints regarding SBC technologies (by date); Downtime of system per month/year; False Accept Rate / False Reject Rate; Total verification time; Total access time; Total time of biometric and document verification).

As regards the last point, this is also in line with FRONTEX’ recommendations related to quality assurance of ABC systems, according to which “for statistical purposes, it is RECOMMENDED to use a minimum amount of anonymised data, such as nationality of the traveller, for each transaction. Storage of personal data identifying the traveller, including the passport number, SHOULD be avoided without proper justification”⁷⁷. Another document of FRONTEX lists the minimum recommended

⁷⁷ FRONTEX, Best Practice Operational Guidelines for Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems, 2015, p.53.

anonymous operational data to be collected for quality assurance and for the extraction of business statistics in ABC systems⁷⁸.

An overview of the planned anonymized statistics that the METICOS consortium envisages to collect from end-users organizations (MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS, CYPOL) is provided in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”. Once the availability of the end-users’ data will be confirmed and in order to ensure that the anonymization processes will be carried out effectively by the end-user organizations before that the information is transmitted to the METICOS platform, it is planned to organize a workshop with MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS and CYPOL. This workshop will be dedicated to discuss the anonymization techniques being applied in order to avoid risks of re-identification. These anonymization techniques will be detailed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

⁷⁸ See section 6 of FRONTEX, Best Practice Technical Guidelines for Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems, 2015.

5 Mitigation measures

For each impact on human rights having been evaluated in the previous section, the table below summarizes the mitigation measures having been identified.

Table 14 - Summary of the identified mitigation measures

Origin of the impact	Explanation	Recommendations/mitigation measures
Potential undercoverage bias due to target groups not adequately represented in the METICOS pilots' and research' samples.	The research results of the METICOS project might be biased in case of insufficient representation of the different impacted groups of persons identified in section 3.	<p>During the pilots, it is recommended to Involve all target groups identified in section 3.1 of this Deliverable.</p> <p>If it is not possible to engage with all of these target groups during the pilots, a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns (for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders to be organized between M17 and M22 – see section 6). This is particularly relevant for children since it was decided not to involve them during the pilots, as their consent to participate would not be considered as freely given (only adults over 18 with a capacity to consent will be able to participate).</p>
The collection and processing by border control technologies of biometric data (facial image, fingerprints) to verify the identity of the document's holder.	The collection and processing of biometric data (facial image, fingerprints) to verify the identity of the document's holder might (or not) appear to be a disproportionate interference with the rights to privacy and data protection, right to non-discrimination, etc.	In the questionnaires (as well as in the METICOS tablet & mobile applications), it is recommended to include questions reflecting the human rights' concerns deriving from the storage of biometrics in travel documents. A draft list of questions has been established in order to be discussed in workshops to be organized with partners and external stakeholders between M17 and M22 (see section 6).

<p>The use by border control technologies of EU large-scale IT systems (SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc.) to databases to determine eligibility of border crossing according to the pre-defined rules.</p>	<p>The use of EU processing of personal data (including biometrics) in centralized IT systems for border control management might appear (or not) to create a disproportionate interference with the rights to privacy and data protection, right to non-discrimination, etc.</p>	<p>In the questionnaires (as well as in the METICOS tablet & mobile applications), it is recommended to include questions reflecting the human rights' concerns deriving from the processing of personal data (including biometrics) in EU large-scale IT systems. A draft list of questions has been established in order to be discussed in workshops to be organized with partners and external stakeholders between M17 and M22 (see section 6).</p>
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the travellers' data within the METICOS platform such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deanonimization of the primary and secondary data being processed by the METICOS platform. • Illegitimate access to primary and secondary data processed by the METICOS platform. 	<p>In case of data breaches in the METICOS platform, border guards' staff might take unfair individual decisions towards travellers. Such decisions might impact different human rights, depending on the concrete circumstances.</p>	<p>A DPIA has been conducted in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”. A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR.</p>
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the border guard staff's data within the METICOS platform.</p>	<p>In case of breaches of border guard's data in the METICOS platform, the staff may be discriminated by their employers.</p>	<p>A DPIA has been conducted in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”. A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the</p>

		measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR.
Potential use of Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) during pilots in order to detect the travellers' acceptance.	Using Facial Emotion Recognition cameras during the pilots might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.	At this stage of the project, it was decided not to use cameras with facial emotion recognition as a data source of the METICOS platform.
The potential collection of data from the travellers' documents by non-authorized border staff.	The collection of data directly from travel documents by non-authorized border staff might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.	At this stage of the project, it was decided not to collect data directly from travel documents. It was considered that it is not necessary for the purposes of the METICOS project to collect information enabling the individualization of each traveler/border control staff member (first name, last name, date of birth, travel document number, etc.).
The potential connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc.	The connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, etc might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such interferences might have impacts on other fundamental rights depending on the concrete circumstances.	At this stage of the project, it was decided not to collect personal data from Border Control Databases such as VIS, SIS, EES, ETIAS, etc. It was considered that such extremely sensitive data were absolutely not needed for the purposes of the project.
The data collection from Twitter and other social media.	Retrieving any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and mining the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies might create	A DPIA has been conducted in D3.1 – "Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)". A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the

	a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such a data processing could also potentially lead to an interference with the freedom of expression.	processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR.
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6 Audit and review of the HRIA

The review and audit stage of a Human Right impact assessment aims at ensuring independent evaluation of the HRIA process and, if necessary, of independent intervention. It especially focuses on the finalisation of the HRIA, by reviewing and assessing whether the process has been successfully conducted and whether the assessor has ensured follow-ups of the relevant findings. However, the review and audit stage also plays a role during the entire HRIA process, for it can steer the process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.

The figure below illustrates the envisaged timeline to proceed to both the review and audit processes of the HRIA.

Figure 4 - HRIA's timeline

The following sub-sections describe the envisaged review and audit processes of the HRIA.

6.1 Review process of the HRIA

The aim of the review stage of the HRIA is to evaluate the findings of this HRIA (as well as the findings of D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)” so as to provide constructive feedback for improving the execution of the HRIA process.

In particular, during the review process, the following issues need to be addressed:

- Are all human rights impacts identified?
- In determining mitigation measures, are all efforts made to first avoid the impact altogether, and if this is not possible to reduce, mitigate and remediate the impacts?

In order to be able to conduct their mission, the reviewers must have sufficient ethical or legal knowledge as well as expertise in the specific research field of project. In addition, the views of independent experts need to be provided. Therefore, the reviewers of this HRIA will be both the

project partners as well as external stakeholders such as lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, etc. It is also important to collect the views of the different groups of persons being impacted by the border control technologies being identified in section 3.1.

It is planned to organize a virtual workshop with partners and the identified external stakeholders between M22 and M29.

The feedback of the reviewers will be reported and taken into account in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”, due on M30.

6.2 Audit process of the HRIA

In addition to the review process described in the previous sub-section, an audit process conducted by the Ethical Board is foreseen with the aim to steer the HRIA process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.

As a reminder, the Ethical Board has been established by D1.8 – “GEN - Requirement No. 11”. The role of the Ethical Board is to independently, ethically and legally monitor the activities and outputs of the project.

As illustrated in figure 3, it is envisaged:

- to ask the Ethical Board’s opinion on D3.2 – “Human rights impact assessment (first version)” before the organization of the review workshop with external stakeholders;
- to ask the Ethical Board’s opinion on the draft of D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)” before the submission of the document to the European Commission on M30.

The views and opinions of the Ethical Board will be reported in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”.

7 Conclusion

The first version of the Human Rights Impact Assessment (HRIA) conducted in this Deliverable is based on the information made available by the METICOS consortium at this stage of the project. Therefore, it should be considered as an interim version.

After having detailed the scope(s) of the HRIA, the target groups and the human rights being impacted, this first version identifies relevant mitigation measures and recommendations in order to avoid the negative impacts altogether, and if this is not possible, to reduce, mitigate and remediate these impacts.

In this first version of the HRIA, it was not feasible yet to host a virtual workshop with partners and external stakeholders (e.g., technical experts, lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, citizens, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, as well as others) to evaluate the findings of this HRIA. This step will be carried out during the review stage of the HRIA between M17 and M22 and with the aim to validate the analysis and suggest additional issues for consideration.

In addition, this version of the HRIA will be submitted for audit to the Ethical Board that has been established by D1.8 – “GEN - Requirement No. 11”. The aim is to steer the HRIA process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.

Being an iterative process, a final version of this DPIA will be provided in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”, which is due on M30.

